

iQonic

iQonic

Innovative strategies, sensing and process chains for increased Quality, re-configurability, and recyclability of Manufacturing Optoelectronics

Deliverable

D2.5 Strategy implementation report

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Deliverable due date: 31/05/2020

Actual submission date: 07/11/2020

Version: v1.0

Document Control Page	
Title	Report on iQonic actual realisation at process-chain and component level
Creator	ATLANTIS
Description	Public strategy implementation report on iQonic realization (due M20) at process-chain and component level.
Contributors	FRAUHOFFER, BRUNEL, CORE, POLIMI, SHADOW, HOLONIX, SENSAP, IP-ASCR/HiLase, PRIMA, ALPES, FORTH, FILAR, SACMI, FICONTEC, TUT, BRIGHTERWAVE.
Creation date	14/03/2019
Type	Report
Language	English
Audience	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> public <input type="checkbox"/> confidential
Review status	<input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> T2.2 leader accepted <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Coordinator accepted
Action requested	<input type="checkbox"/> to be revised by Partners <input type="checkbox"/> for approval by the WP leader <input type="checkbox"/> for approval by the Project Coordinator <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> for acknowledgement by Partners

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY / ABSTRACT

The following deliverable is report of the iQonic project funded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, under the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation action programme (H2020) reporting the results of the activities carried out by *T2.5 Monitoring of iQonic strategies implementation and risk analysis*. This task T2.5 is focused on development of components and process chains levels implementation (with respect to the eight iQonic strategies) as well as their adaptation at ALPES, PRIMA, FILAR and BRIGHTERWAVE and system operational environment as well as their actual realisation at system-component development. Furthermore, this process chain status measurement analysis will be adapted to provide the very first and draft means for process validation and deployment that will be revised, completed and finalised throughout tasks *T7.2 Technology Validation* and *T7.3 Solution Validation through demonstration in relevant environment*. Note must be made that the monitoring of iQonic strategy implementation and deployment runs in parallel with the development of tasks within the WP3-WP6 and the respective report will be delivered summarising the observation obtained during the lifetime of this task and due M20.

SCOPE

Within the work at this project, strategies are designed and will be deployed at ALPES, PRIMA, FILAR and BRIGHTERWAVE in order to DIAGNOSE and ADJUST the system requirements for new parts and products with respective processes, PREDICT / DETECT / PREVENT / SUSTAIN defects, MANAGE alarms and mitigation actions and REDESIGN for sustainability in order to ensure better disassembly, recycling and requalification of the currently irreversible optical properties. The ultimate goal of this holistic approach is to increase sustainability, flexibility, accurately diagnoses of production requirements of new opto-electrical parts and to adjust process chains hence to predict and to prevent propagation of defects as well as to reintroduce into the value chains products and parts at their end of life.

ABBREVIATIONS

Return on Investment	ROI
Research and Development	R&D
Technology Readiness Levels	TRL
Red-Green-Blue	RGB
Electrostatic Discharge	ESD
Key Performance Indicators	KPI
Decision Support System	DSS
Manufacturing Execution Systems	MES
Technical Objectives	TO
Non-Destructive Testing	NDT
Cyber-Physical System	CPS
Knowledge Base System	KBS
Key Performance Factor	KPF
Manufacturing Execution System	MES
International Organization for Standardization	ISO

WorkStation Level	WSL
Part Level	PL
Shop-floor and Plant level	SPL
Critical to Quality	CTQ
Small and medium-sized enterprises	SME
Internet of Things	IoT
Overall Performance Indicators	OPI
Software	s/w
Hardware	h/w
User Experience	UX
Create, read, update and delete	CRUD
Reveres Supply Chain	RSC
Support Vector Machine	SVM
Higher Level Communication Middleware	HLCM
Minimum Viable Product	MVP
Research and Development	R&D
State of the Art	SoA
Accelerated Lifetime Testing	ALT
Requirements	RQs
New Product Introduction	NPI

1 Introduction

Optoelectronics and opto-electrical components involve the interactions of photons and electrons that are used in parts such as lasers, photodiodes, image sensors, optical amplifiers, modulators, solar cells, embedded optics and light-emitting diodes. iQonic will deal with optoelectronics, namely design and production of photodiodes by ALPES, assembly of medium sized lasers for manufacturing by PRIMA and miniaturized laser modules for augmented reality by BRIGHTERWAVE, and the design and development of optical amplifiers and crystals by FILAR. The overall process chain optimisation, along with the smart handling tool, the adaptive optics, iLike Machines, event modelling, Reverse Supply Chain (RSC) and Decision Support Systems (DSS), Integration automation and Inspection Kit, Electronic nose and Cyber Physical Systems (CPS) are technologies that are used in iQonic optoelectronics.

The new process will be introduced into production systems that will adjust many processes in order to fit the production of complex components. The adjustments include both component specific changes as well as standard process steps. Due to the need to produce large varieties of parts in small batches but also a huge amount of communication laser assemblies, process adjustments have to be both rapid and accurate while the equipment for testing, failure analysis and control equipment need to follow a fast pace of technical advancement and cover a range of sensors, such as electrical, optical, magnetic and thermal sensors.

The impact of iQonic to the European opto-electronics manufacturing industry and society itself will be a result of obtained after the four years. It is known that presently, the optoelectrical manufacturing is facing significant challenges in dealing with the evolution of the equipment, instrumentation and manufacturing processes they support. The vision of this H2020 project is to increase of the in-service efficiency by 22%, flexibility by 16% faster reconfiguration times, to obtain 10% reduction in production costs through recycled components and materials, to improve designs for assembly and disassembly as well as to create about 400 new jobs and have over 39M EUR Return on Investment (ROI) for the consortium. The purpose of this deliverable, *D2.5 Strategy Implementation Report*, is to provide a specific description of iQonic strategies, present/initial system of deployment and system adaptation as well as iQonic actual realisation at process chain and component level and their estimation of the delivery (deployment) due M20.

1.1 Scope and structure

The iQonic project will be working on new processes applicable to the production of opto-electrical components, e.g. material handling, material strain engineering, patterning, material deposition, assembly, joining and bonding. Furthermore, quality will be ensured by reliable sensors throughout the production line while the processes will include a level of sustainability (recycling of high value components provides also financial motivation) that allows the final products to be recycled and reintroduced into the value chain. This new, flexible and innovative process chains will handle complex designs that include opto-electrical functionalities where improved sensor equipment for quality control in the different processing steps as well as the final functionality of the component will be involved.

The work obtained in this task has been presented within respective sections of this deliverable in the following way:

- Overall approach, plan and methodology of iQonic as well as its schematic methodology,
- Description and correlation among iQonic Strategies, components (exploitable results) and Technical Objectives (TO) as well as milestones that needs to be completed due M20,
- Quality management systems standard and data collection principles (ISO standards),
- Initial plan of system deployment in pilots as well as their scenarios adaptation of iQonic system,
- Conclusion and next steps and
- Appendix with technical and non-technical requirements of iQonic system.

2 Overall approach and methodology of iQonic

iQonic project has the goal to develop a holistic framework that is applicable to new and to existing manufacturing lines of opto-electronics that bring industry to zero-defect production, achieving the flexibility and sustainability. During the 42 months of work in this project, iQonic follows several dynamic activities in order to achieve this challenging and inspiring vision: research and development (R&D), demonstration at pilot sites, dissemination and exploitation of results and various management activities. The schematic methodology representation is depicted in Figure 2-1 where of overall iQonic approach and plan, is presented on details as following:

- Technology generation and experimentation phase includes all the R&D activities for the development of iQonic sub-systems.
- Integration and validation of the technologies phase involves all the integration activities that will be performed during the project where the goal is to prepare the system for its validation as a full prototype.
- Demonstration of the iQonic results phase offers vital input to make any necessary adjustments before deploying the system in the real industrial use-cases where the first step is the demonstration of the validated technologies in the use-cases while the ultimate one is the iQonic prototype demonstration in the relevant environments (TRL6).
- Project and Technical Management, Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication activities runs the whole duration of the project in order to keep track of all the involved activities and take action when is required that will ensure the smooth progress of all the R&D and demonstration activities as well as efficient planning for commercialisation and dissemination of the results throughout the duration of each phase.

Figure 2-1: Overall approach and methodology of iQonic

This task T2.5 is focused on development of vertical (component level) and horizontal (process chains level) implementation, with respect to the iQonic strategies (sub-section 2.1) concept, their adaptation at each pilot scenario (section 4) and system operational environment as well as their actual realisation at system-component development. Furthermore, this process chain status measurement analysis will be adapted to provide the very first means for process validation and deployment. Note must be made that the monitoring of iQonic strategy implementation runs in parallel with the development of tasks within WP3-WP6 due M20 of the projects life time as pointed at Figure 1-1 (blue square).

2.1 Strategies, Architecture's Components and Technical Objectives

The holistic framework of iQonic solution will be demonstrated and applied in environment of laser diodes manufacturing, crystal production, laser systems for industrial application and the manufacturers of red-green-blue (RGB) miniaturized laser modules for augmented reality. The project concept offers a scalable zero-defect manufacturing platform covering the overall process chain, ranging from the design of new opto-electrical components and their required optimised process chain, their assembly process, to their disassembly and reintroduction into the value chain at their end-of-life. Following this idea, industries will achieve and increased yields (low and high-volume productions), faster reconfiguration times accommodating more designs and reintroduction of recycled components to reduce the material costs. Consequently, iQonic will comprise new hardware (h/w) and software (s/w) components (*D2.2 SoA analysis of assembly processes in respect of demonstrators*) interfaced with the current facilities through internet of things (IoT) and data management platforms, while being managed through scalable strategies at component, workstation and shop floor level.

Figure 2-2: Synergies and interactions between iQonic strategies

In summary, the eight iQonic scalable strategies (Figure 2-2) target:

- early detection of the design characteristics (DIAGNOSE),
- adaptation of the process chains (ADJUST),
- early detection of the defect (DETECT),
- prediction of the defect generation (PREDICT),
- prevention of defect generation by recalibrating the production line (multi-stage), as well as defect propagation in later stages of the production (PREVENT),
- reworking/remanufacturing of the product, if this is possible, and their re-use and/or requalification (SUSTAIN),
- management of the aforementioned strategies through event modelling, KPI (key performance indicators) monitoring and real-time decision support (MANAGE),
- provision of feedback for the design performance and defects leading to better products and process chains (REDESIGN).

The developed strategies will be activated based on detecting and assessing the impact of system level events that cause lower quality, generate defects, and increase the costs. This iQonic approach exploits all the acquired data from which a prediction is made. Following, details of these strategies are provided below.

DIAGNOSE

When a new part is planned to be produced, this strategy is introduced whose aim is to prepare sensors and other data collection sources, as well as to make monitoring system to take into account the different characteristics of each product. Based on the material sensitivity (i.e. brittle, soft, delicate, fragile), the ESD and the contamination sensitivity, a mapping takes place while the design is analysed to prepare the system to the given geometry (i.e. cylindrical, complex 3D shape), its surface (i.e. smooth, sticky, tangled) and last the weight and dimensions based on the design. Taking into account the parameters above-mentioned (among others), the system will be able to avoid generating defects by developing a system model which will be fed to the strategy PREDICT in order to simulate the given scenario and identify possible failures.

PREDICT

From the physical layer of the system, the events are detected and engineered into high value data that will specify new and more accurate process models. This behaviour of monitoring and analysis, enriches the existing knowledge of the system learning new patterns, raising attention towards performance that cause alarms and the general trends in the shop-floor. While the data pool is being increased, the precise repeatability and accurate predictions are also improved. The estimations for the future states involve the machine status after several number of operations and a quality of the products for given set of parameters (entire production line). With high confidence (based on defects), the system will try to predict the expected quality and customer satisfaction while allowing parameters to be modified before the production of the products. Furthermore, iQonic can operate in the reverse mode, (i.e. insert a Customer Satisfaction Goal) and control the parameters accordingly to achieve this target. iQonic will have the ability to optimise the manufacturing processes according to certain and target quality levels and/or customer satisfaction that is the key innovation fulfilling the industrial requirements.

ADJUST

The parameters of the system will be identified and DIAGNOSED where they have been applied within the system model. The specific production requirements for each new part will be highlighted and stored in the system, examining the initial set-up while comparing the resulted outcomes from the PREDICT strategy. The process continues iteratively until the predicted quality is acceptable when the final parameters are forwarded to MANAGE strategy. This will make the final decision on the actions and the Manufacturing planning and management system will be informed that the parameters are ready for employment. Finally, the parameters are stored in order to be correlated with the actual outcome while being flagged accordingly in order to improve the accuracy of the future system iterations.

PREVENT

The quality control and the inspection tools realised across the shop floor, for condition monitoring of machinery and respective produced quality, are part of the prevention of defects strategy where PREDICT is predecessor of PREVENT. Into consideration, the initial estimation of the future states and expected outcomes are considered while modelling of the parameters takes place where for each predicted defect, the responsible parameters are identified and flagged. The system adapts these parameters based on an initial estimation, which after the simulation these are corrected recursively. The outcome of this process is to avoid the generation of defects that is based on each recorded event (e.g. defect, no defect, low quality, high-quality) both from previous and current states. Furthermore, the false alarms will be reduced by the system demonstrating and combining the future predictions.

DETECT

While a defect is being generated and after the adaptation of the parameters, this strategy is being activated. Firstly, an alarm is being triggered in order to highlight the parameters that resulted in a defect where the system will be able to avoid having more generated defects by weighting the system model. Furthermore, the strategy involves more actions and processes to deal both with the generation of the detected defect and its propagation to the next stages. Depending on the station that the defect was generated, the system will adapt its parameters to the previous successful state and plan to send the defected product either to downstream or upstream stage where the final decision on the actions is based on the MANAGE strategy.

MANAGE

The MANAGE strategy is responsible for the overall supervision and optimisation of the system where the defects are processed by the Decision Support System (DSS) tools and interfaced with Manufacturing Execution Systems (MES). After the DETECT strategy, false positives and false negatives are clustered resulting into a good filtering of these false alarms. In order to do this, the previous acquired knowledge and incidents are also processed to regulate the system's operation. Moreover, the production is optimised by better scheduling, taking into account the environmental impact of each process while the adaptability of the manufacturing improves the overall flexibility, placing a premium on the production rates, satisfying the demand and preserve increased machinery availability. The knowledge management system will tune the whole production according to certain quality levels and customer satisfaction where the strategy involves the decision making in the event of a defect. The inspection system will analyse defect classifying and categoring it based on its' severity and deciding if the product is to be (a) reworked on spot or to be (b) removed from the production line for further inspection and rework. Consequently, for the defect classified as "non-repairable", the system will decide to (a) forward the product to the upstream stages or to (b) consider the defect as a total failure where the product will be recycled.

SUSTAIN

This strategy is activated, when a "repairable" defect is detected, deploying a proper and customized repairing action with minimum time and effort, assuring the best productivity and production flow (automatically repair the occurred defects without perturbing the overall production flow). By developing the a model-based supervisory control solution, the iQonic will be able to interpret the inter-stage quality control measurements together with the monitoring of the process itself, in order to identify the defect sources and generate a proper and customized repairing action. To facilitate the implementation of the eight strategies, a policy to support a "reverse supply-chain" is involved (in the context of a multi-stage supply-chain attached to a multi-stage production. Finally, the defected products/parts detected and produced during a stage, or provided from suppliers in a particular stage (in downstream stag) could be returned to internal or external supply-chain tiers (upstream stages) for part remanufacturing or part recycling.

REDESIGN

The only strategy linked with MANAGE, without interfering or affecting the other six, is REDESIGN that provides feedback and knowledge to future products and iterations. Obtained lessons learnt from the employed process chains for each design are to be analysed as described providing recommendations and suggestions for improvements. Sustainability and recyclability redesigns, for will allow next parts to reduce defects while optimising the production processes and preserving their functionalities, considering their disassembly, recycling at their end of life. Furthermore, during the production and at any time, as well as during the validation and/or usage, the derived knowledge from all the stages will ensure that the future designs will be more sustainable, with better quality and maximised customer satisfaction.

Subsequent, each of the above described and developed strategies in the project will be triggered based on detecting and assessing the impact of system level events that cause lower quality, generate defects and

increase the costs. The iQonic approach is considered to be holistic and it utilizes all the acquired data from which a prediction is made with very high confidence levels.

During the work in task T2.2, the deliverable *D2.2 SoA analysis of assembly processes in respect of demonstration* have identified the technologies used for delivering iQonic presenting the State of the Art. The work T2.3 and deliverable *D2.3 iQonic system architecture process chain & Strategies* presents s/w and h/w components in details that will be developed in the project (WP3-WP6). Furthermore, Technical Objectives (TO) described and presented in details in *D2.1 User Requirements* are closely followed, allowing the optoelectronic industry to implement eight zero-defect manufacturing strategies (previously described) in order to increase quality, re-configurability and recyclability. TO and their validation statuses due M20 have been followed and monitored by Technical Manager and the validation statuses are summarized in Table 2-1.

Table 2-1: Technical Objectives Validation Statuses

TO	Brief Description	Technical Objectives Validation (Y/N)
TO1	Development of diagnostic system for adjustment of production processes.	Y
TO2	Development of continuous monitoring of the condition and performance.	Y
TO3	Employment of a highly flexible handling tool.	Y
TO4	Employ a smart tag scanning process between the production stages.	Y
TO5	Develop a reliable and precise non-destructive sensing system.	Y
TO6	Develop a radical new design for sustainability process chain.	Y
TO7	Develop a machine learning system to predict quality.	Y
TO8	Introduction of a self-adjusted inference engine.	Y
TO9	Development of a higher-level Decision Support System.	Y
TO10	Integrate different strategies for production monitoring and quality control.	Y
TO11	Widespread adoption of iQonic results.	Y

In details, the modelling of the processes and the design of the overall process chain to respect the sensitivity and the other characteristics of each component (surface, size, etc.) is a great leap forward by iQonic (TO1, TO7). The introduction of a smart grasping hand (TO3) combined with the assembly design (O6), to include the requirements of the patterning, material deposition, joining, alignment and bonding, unified under a single modelling system, will ensure high quality products. In addition, iQonic will introduce highly accurate sensors (TO4, TO5) and a holistic monitoring system throughout the production (TO2) to allow sustainability in the production. In addition, iQonic involves a novel reverse supply chain and recyclability aspects (TO6) to ensure the components reintroduction into the value chain at their end-of-life (TO10). Furthermore, iQonic will not only be capable of producing various designs through strong diagnostics (TO1), but also a series of sensors and equipment to orchestrate the processes accordingly (TO3, TO5, TO6). Moreover, the system will monitor the quality of the components in all the processing steps (TO2) while their processing with new sensors (TO5) and a modelling of the whole process chain for increased quality (TO7) will ensure functional components. The detection of defects throughout the production (TO8) will increase the performance which combined with the modelling to inspect quality according to each preselected settings (TO7) will be correlated with the in-processes NDT sensors (TO5) in order to create a reliable and accurate system and five strategies (PREDICT, DETECT, PREVENT, SUSTAIN, MANAGE) are designed to maximise the quality levels. In addition,

intelligent algorithms and robust decision support system (TO9) will ensure that the production line will have high performance, accuracy and fidelity. Finally, the design for sustainability and reverse supply chain scheme (TO6) will ensure the reuse of precious materials and products and the final three iQonic strategies (SUSTAIN, MANAGE, and REDESIGN) will ensure the reusability and requalification of the products. All the above with the support from the consortium partners was used to summarise the correlation of iQonic strategies and corresponding components and tools as well as the TO of this project (Table 2-2).

Table 2-2: Component (exploitable result), TO and iQonic strategy correlation

Organizations	Component	Technical Objectives (TO)	iQonic Strategy
FRAUNHOFER	Process chain optimised designs for micro-macro assembly and disassembly	TO1, TO2, TO5, TO6, TO10, TO11	DIAGNOSE, ADJUST, PREDICT, DETECT, PREVENT, SUSTAIN, MANAGE, REDESIGN
ATLANTIS	Defect Severity Decision Support System	TO1, TO2, TO3, TO5, TO6, TO7, TO8, TO9, TO10	DIAGNOSE, DETECT, ADJUST, PREDICT, PREVENT, MANAGE, REDESIGN
	Reverse Supply Chain Process Strategy	TO3, TO5, TO6, TO9, TO10	DETECT, SUSTAIN, MANAGE, REDESIGN
	Higher Level Communication Middleware	TO4, TO6, TO8, TO9, TO10	MANAGE, REDESIGN
BRUNEL	A data modelling platform capable of real-time operation that exhibits optimal performance and system stability	TO2, TO7, TO8	DETECT, PREDICT, PREVENT, MANAGE, REDESIGN
CORE	Early malfunction detection and prediction inference engine	TO7, TO8, TO9, TO10	DIAGNOSE, PREDICT, DETECT, PREVENT, MANAGE
POLIMI	Cyber Physical System for feed-forward control of multi-stage process chains	TO3, TO5, TO6, TO7, TO9, TO10	DETECT, PREVENT, MANAGE, ADJUST
SHADOW	Modular grasping hardware supporting a range of production assembly and tuning tasks	TO3, TO11	ADJUST
HOLONIX	New iLike Machine Platform functionalities	TO2, TO4	DIAGNOSE, MANAGE
	Knowledge Based System	TO2, TO4	DIAGNOSE, MANAGE
SENSAP	New functionalities of Integra Traceability Kit Product	TO2, TO4	DIAGNOSE, MANAGE

HiLASE/IP-ASCR	Thin-disk head	TO2, TO6, TO11	DIAGNOSE, ADJUST, PREDICT, DETECT, PREVENT, SUSTAIN, MANAGE, REDESIGN
FORTH	Inspection systems that based on adaptive optics	TO5	DETECT, DIAGNOSE
FICONTEC	Flexible high precision assembly system with increased yield	TO2, TO7, TO8, TO9, TO10	DIAGNOSE, ADJUST, PREDICT, DETECT, PREVENT, SUSTAIN, MANAGE, REDESIGN
SACMI	Olfactory system for detecting contamination	TO5	DIAGNOSE, DETECT
TAT	Active and passive component bonding processes in micro-optics	TO6, TO11	DIAGNOSE, ADJUST, PREDICT, DETECT, PREVENT, SUSTAIN, MANAGE, REDESIGN

Milestones (MS), the goals within this project have been defined and are to be met and completed due specific due date and reasonable time. The details i.e. deadlines and means of milestone verifications are presented in the Table 2-3. Note must be that the tasks end life finished due month M20 where the milestone MS3.2, MS5.1 and MS6.1 will be partially followed as respectfully they are due M22 and M33.

Table 2-3: List of milestones for WP3-WP6 due M24

Milestone number	Milestone title	WP	Lead beneficiary	Due Month	Means of verification
MS3	MS3.1	WP3	TAT	M15	Finalised opto-electrical system design for assembly/disassembly: The optoelectrical functionalities of the different components are listed, and the requirements for Sensitivity, Geometry, Material, Size are considered to arrange the assembly and disassembly processes with the respective sensory analysed.
MS4	MS3.2	WP3	TAT	M22	Automatically load the final parameterisation of the processes: Delivery of D3.3 and D3.4 with the interfaces to incorporate quality control information and in-process information and optoelectrical functionalities, that need to be controlled and protected. These will be loaded automatically with smart tagging between the stages.
MS5	MS4.1	WP4	SENSAP	M19	In-line sensors and Handling tool are ready: The in-line sensors of electronic nose, and the adaptive optics are validated in the laboratory and ready for integration. The Handling tool is validated and ready to be interfaced with the rest systems.
MS6	MS4.2	WP4	HOLONIX	M19	KBS and Data management system: The infrastructure and the data from the sensors and actuators are connected with the KBS to combine historical and current data for tested

					and validated accurate fast-forward forecasting.
MS7	MS5.1	WP5	POLIMI	M33	DSS for reuse and requalification of components: Both DSS and CPS for the reverse supply chain (RSC) schema and reuse requalification of components and materials is integrated and tested as a single framework.
MS8	MS6.1	WP6	BRUNEL	M33	Integrated intelligent engine interfaced with MES: The detection and prediction engine of the machine states is integrated with the event modelling of the KPFs and tested. The integrated engine is successfully communicating with MES.

2.2 ISO Standards

During the proposal phase, several standards have been analysed, considered and followed in this project. In general, standards are providing the tangible assistance and measurable benefit to almost every possible sector reinforcing the technology that we depend on, ensuring the expected quality. ISO guidelines and various documents provide requirements, specifications, characteristics that can be constantly used in order to ensure that materials, products, processes and services are matching the purpose. When thinking of product/parts and data gathering processes two standards (mentioned below) are followed and applied.

2.2.1 ISO 9001:2015

To apply and to adopt a quality management system is a strategic decision for an organisation that can advance and improve its overall performance as well as to deliver its strong and sustainable development initiative. The quality management system requirements specified in this ISO standard are complementary to requirements for products and services. This specific and international quality management systems standard¹, specifies two requirements for an organisation to follow. First, the standard stipulates that a company needs to demonstrate its capability to consistently provide products and services that meet customer and applicable regulatory requirements while aiming to enhance customer satisfaction through the effective application of the system by including processes for improvement of the system assuring the conformity to customer and applicable statutory and regulatory requirements. The quality management system consists of interrelated processes and its understanding how results are produced by this system enables an organization to optimize the system and its performance².

2.2.2 ISO 14224:2016

This ISO standard³ provides a complete source for the collection of reliability and maintenance (RM) data in standard format for equipment in all facilities and operations (for petroleum, natural gas and petrochemical industries) during the operational life cycle of equipment. The standard describes data collection principles and associated terms and definitions, data quality control and assurance practices to provide guidance for the user. This practice facilitates exchanging the information among plants, owners, manufacturers and contractors, defining the minimum amount of data that needs to be collected focussing on data requirements for the categories of data to be collected and used in several methodologies of analysis.

¹ <https://www.sis.se/api/document/preview/919487/>

² <https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/archive/pdf/en/pub100080.pdf>

³ <https://www.sis.se/api/document/preview/920899/>

3 General and Initial plan of iQonic deployment

During the proposal phase, iQonic defined three functional and inspection systems that correspond to the respective levels of pilots: I) WorkStation Level (WSL), II) Part Level (PL) and III) Shop-floor and Plant level (SPL). These levels will be supported by the zero-defect scalable framework of the iQonic system that will operate over the levels allowing the implementation of reactive, coordination and cognitive functions through smart services. Figure 3-3 presents these levels where note must be made that, the strategies are distributed throughout the manufacturing line and therefore these cannot be depicted as single blocks. Following, the Reactive Functions are intended for fast reaction and close to machine operation (condition monitoring) while the Cognitive Functions are intended for rich condition, quality, sensitivity monitoring and quality prediction, as well as for suitable production strategy identification. They are using reactive functions outputs, collective intelligence development through collaborative analytics for behaviours of the material, the shape, the functionalities, and the integrated information framework regarding the defects and the overall process. The Coordination Functions are the critical element in closing the iQonic loop bringing to life remediate strategies through concrete dynamic production plans and production control in the form of specific processes chains to be executed on production.

Figure 3-3: Involved iQonic processes and linked stages

Work Station Level (WSL) and its process of implementation require condition monitoring technologies of the machines (i.e. sensors and actuators embedded or installed around the machines) specialised in gathering the intrinsic and extrinsic machine’s key performance parameters (KPI). For iQonic pilots there is a different set of internal parameters representing each factor that affects the machine’s behaviour on system level (e.g. structural health, degradation of components, production rate, temperature, vibration, etc) and external parameters involving factors that affect the machine’s performance but are not in the system level (e.g. ambient conditions, ambient temperature, humidity, operator’s or system’s inputs, etc) that are defined and reported in *D1.4 iQonic Use Cases*. At the WSL, the system involves monitoring of the in-process actions meaning that all the produced parts will not only be examined as the output of the machine i.e. during quality inspection, but also during their processing. A series of sensors will monitor the procedures, involving measurements for the ambient conditions (e.g. pressure, temperature, etc) as well as the behaviour of each design based on its unique characteristics (e.g. material, ESD and contamination, sensitivity, its geometry, physical characteristics). In order to do that, a laser to be designed to receive feedback during operation will be implemented in collaboration with the already installed sensors to track the aforementioned conditions. Furthermore, the system will introduce an innovative odour sensor to track the alterations occurring on the

material on a chemical basis. The knowledge derived from these sensors, will allow to evaluate the material and the functional properties of the products while is being produced and not after. Of course, this overall idea, will be revised and updated throughout the lifetime of the project.

At **Part Level (PL)**, lasers and cameras will monitor the quality of each product, according to the requirements for each iQonic Use Case where, for each of the processes, will be decided which areas will be inspected as well as the time available for such inspections. The goal is to ensure that each product conforms to the pre-defined upper and lower acceptable quality limits (i.e. Critical to Quality – CTQ). To this end, the repeatability is a critical indicator, which will be monitored using statistics with the goal to categorise the products in quality classes. All of the produced results will be stored according to the quality inspection based on the requested, expected and actual quality. The actions will be aligned with the Quality Management Systems (sub-section 2.2.1) aiming at constant improvement to meet requirements from the customer and the industrial stakeholders. Furthermore, this level also facilitates improved handling, alignment and feeding at Gripper sublevel to endow flexibility involving all the processes for material handling-alignment during the production of individual parts as well as during the assembly of optoelectronic parts into a single product. The adjustments needed to handle the material properly according to its ESD requirements, material sensitivity, as well as its contamination will employ different tools to avoid generation of a defect. Geometry and surface characteristics of a component will be recognised before entering the production process in order to take them into account and change the grasping point and end-effector accordingly. In addition, the size and weight of the product will also adjust the handling tools in order to avoid damaging or hurting the product. Since sensitivity is of great importance to the opto-electrical components, the handling and feeding tools will take into account all these requirements and try allowing faster assembling and bonding of individual components. Consequently, iQonic monitoring capabilities will ensure real-time adjustments to a highly flexible and precise grasping hand (e.g. FILAR use case), with multiple end-effectors to cover the requirements for each sensitivity case with different handling approach.

Shop-floor & Plant Level (SPL)

When talking of data gathering, they are produced throughout the process along with the inspection of the production line and will be logged into servers with time indexes where wireless or cable transmission of data will be achieved through a local area network. However, in order to avoid the loss of data, each of the gathered information will be stored to the hard drives following a defined filing structure and naming system throughout all the stages. IoT techniques will facilitate the gathering and sharing of information among different devices in real-time, allowing the decision makers for fast and accurate mitigation actions. In addition, the process actions for each design along with the predicted quality will also be stored into the system, storing information about the machine performance and its actual status, based on specifications, prediction of adjustments and actions and historical data. iQonic will be aligned with the collection and exchange of reliability and maintenance data for equipment (sub-section 2.2.2) regarding the requirements for the categories of data to be collected for use in various analysis methodologies. These elements will allow that iQonic strategies can be easily integrated over legacy machines and information technologies systems with minimum interference and that even SMEs are able to easily integrate advanced zero-defect manufacturing processes.

Knowledge Management and semantic modelling system will provide “wisdom” to the iQonic approach by making use of historical data and the acquired knowledge for all the operations occurred. It will comprise the modelling of machines and products, the respective actions and processes, as well as the readings from sensors and metrology infrastructure entities such as CTQ structures, etc. In order to maximize the prognostic capabilities of the system, for every new set of measurements it will be possible to assess the accuracy of the predictions by comparing them against the actual status (sensor readings and the system analysis). Moreover, the previous alarm activations will be correlated against the predicted and actual quality outcomes, in order to assess the level of false positives and false negatives (i.e. false alarms). The knowledge derived from this analysis will be used to improve the next system’s iterations and enhance the alarm triggering. Therefore, by

incorporating the lessons learnt it is envisaged that the predictions for the future products will have increased accuracy. In addition, iQonic “wisdom” will also filter the activation of alarms, reducing false indications and increase the confidence and safety levels.

Intelligence and learning system will receive input from all the rest acting as the iQonic brain, which will provide feedback for all the processes executed in the production line. This system comprises an event modelling algorithm to identify the parameters from the overall production line which affect the Overall Performance Indicators (OPI) (e.g. customer satisfaction, product quality, energy consumption, inventory control, environmental impact). This system also comprises a DSS and data management algorithms that will allow the evaluation of each performance and accurately adjust the production for different products as well as predict possible defects keeping historical data, as well as to provide self-assessment and learning capabilities, and decide on/recommend the intelligent strategies to activate at each time. What-if capabilities will allow the production planners to find the most effective and cost-efficient processes according to each part and component built. In addition, the executed production Strategies and the physical examination of results (i.e. from experts in the Quality control) will also be stored for “Learning purposes” in order to improve efficiency of future recommendations for Strategies to be activated. Activation of Strategies will aim at addressing defect prediction/detection/.../management, in order to avoid them and ultimately prevent their propagation to downstream stages, or even to ameliorate and mitigate the consequences from their occurrence.

Furthermore, this system will provide a dynamic production plan identifying the design requirements on e.g. geometry, surface, material, weight and dimensions, taking into account the sensitivity of the material (brittle to soft), electrostatic discharge (ESD) sensitivity, and last the contamination sensitivity in order to employ the process chains for feeding, handling based on the above. In addition, the most typical “defects” in the assembly are that the bond has poor quality or the alignment is not within the tolerances (if the confidence level of the components is good) where the requirements are related to the components in the assembly separately or in the case where the components itself are the most likely cause of the defect. Besides, the handling tool will be trained not only to grip the components based on its aforementioned sensitivities but also to respect the optical properties of the system when it’s partially aligned during assembly. Last, an interface with higher level plant management systems will be established (i.e. through deployment of the MANAGE Strategy; cf. also to WP6/T6.4), for exchanging data knowledge and alarms, in order to optimally schedule production activities and re-adapt the process scheduling.

3.1 iQonic technologies status and delivery estimation

iQonic technologies developed within the project (WP3-WP6) will be integrated (WP7) into the final solution that will be implemented (WP8) into optoelectronic manufacturing scenarios of ALPES, PRIMA, FILAR and BRIGHTERWAVE and verified covering the identified needs and requirements of the involved cases. State of the Art (SoA) as well as technical details of these technologies are respectfully provided in details in corresponding deliverables *D2.2 SoA analysis of assembly processes in respect of demonstrators* and *D2.3 iQonic system architecture process chain & Strategies*. Within this section, each of these technologies that are common to all iQonic pilots, are briefly described and their current development status, required input and estimation of technology are summarised and presented in the following Tables 3-4 to 3-19.

According to the iQonic use case scenarios the technologies provide different functionalities that will be used by our end users on their shop floors that will be utilized within the context of the procedures performed at each scenario. Thus, iQonic could be implemented in all end users’ business scenarios or as a partial iQonic case (to be elaborated within WP8).

Table 3-4: Process chain optimised designs for micro-macro assembly and disassembly (FRAUNHOFER)

Technology Description
Optimized photonic assembly processes (hardware-based) – in particular regarding the handling of sensitive opto-electronical components, software-driven online process diagnosis based on a variety of sensor data acquired during all steps of the component preparation and manipulation during assembly. An adaption of processes to actual component data, process statistics and assembly environment information. Management and control of component usage throughout preparation, assembly, product lifetime and recycling of products.
Status
The hardware as well as the software architecture is defined, in particular regarding building blocks in the hardware for assembly and in the software (sensor network, middleware, higher-level intelligence). The generic architecture now shall be implemented by adapting it to the selected use cases.
Required input
Component data from preparation and manipulation, process data throughout the assembly process chain, results from higher level intelligence calculations for modifying actual and later process steps during assembly.
Delivery Estimation
The first generic version is available, and will be adapted to the use case scenarios in WP7.

Table 3-5: Defect Severity Decision Support System (ATLANTIS)

Technology Description
Defect Severity DSS offers improved optimisation of process chains operation vs. defect management (Strategies for improved defect life-cycle management, including recommendations for mitigation actions on identified defects). The system also includes the respective KPIs for severity detection and risk management and measures the user's responses to the DSS suggestions. The suggestions are measured in order to train the system for better results in the implementation of the algorithms.
Status
The first version of the Defect Severity DSS is in test mode. The system needs to be integrated with other components, communicate with them and receive the data. Dedicated API will be developed, which will integrate all the main communication protocols. The learning algorithms for the defect management, which lead to preventive maintenance, are tested against training data. Also, preventive rule – based algorithms are implemented, but there is the need for improvement based on the project's data. Other functionalities, such as graphical representation of rule – based logic and data hotloading will be implemented in further DSS versions, which will be gradually integrated with the whole iQonic system. The system will also incorporate autonomous and hierarchical decision support, database design and schema development, failure modes and asset types incorporation and enhancements of the User Experience (UX).
Required input
The system requires processed data in the form of prediction from other components, in order to work in its rule – based logic. Furthermore, it could need sensorial data as training data sets to the implemented algorithms. The required input should be available in a JSON format file and it includes the prediction 4tuple: asset, failure mode, prediction (number or %) and the timeframe the prediction is valid. Besides, the system is able to process real time or historical sensorial data with great accuracy and produce suggestions based on machine learning algorithms.
Delivery Estimation
The first version of the system is ready to be tested locally in developer's mode. When testing is concluded, the system will be delivered to the end users by M25. Component integration with the rest the iQonic system will be concluded by M29. At the end of the M31 the final DSS version will be integrated and delivered to the end users for testing and evaluation. The latest version of the system (M33) will include more features, new characteristics and implemented end users' recommendations.

Table 3-6: Reverse Supply Chain Process Strategy (ATLANTIS)

Technology Description
Reveres Supply Chain (RSC) offers strategy and policy to be taken based on detected defects, that support decision-making on process flows (e.g. return to supplier, return to previous stage for repair, dispose/recycle) of defected items, in multistage production.
Status
The first version of the RSC is in test mode. The system's basic functions are fully implemented (Statistics, Product Types, Defects, Defect Types, Defect Causes, etc.) and the data is being displayed correctly. Database interaction is working well and create, read, update and delete (CRUD) operations are functional. The Machine Learning method that will be used for the predictive function, will likely be Support Vector Machine (SVM), and is currently being discussed and looked into. In its appropriate format the data can be consumed by the system.
Required input
The system is able to process historical sensorial data with great accuracy. Furthermore, it also needs sensorial data as training data sets in order to implement the machine learning-based predictive function. Additionally, since Cyber Physical System (CPS) will be used to evaluate both the functionality and integrity in order to proceed to downstream stages or upstream, RSC will consume the related data from CPS through HLCM. The required input should be available in JSON format.
Delivery Estimation
The first version of the system is ready to be tested locally in developer's mode while the system will be delivered to the end users by M25. RSC will be integrated with the rest of the iQonic system due month M29. At the end of the M31, the final component version will be integrated, delivered and deployed to the end users for testing and evaluation. The latest version of the system in M33 will include more features, new characteristics and implemented end users' feedback.

Table 3-7: Higher Level Communication Middleware (ATLANTIS)

Technology Description
Higher Level Communication Middleware (HLCM) is related to the design of communication interface with Manufacturing Execution System (MES) and other higher-level management systems (for exchanging data, alarms about predicted/detected defects, recommendations, production and product requirements).
Status
Requirements of the pilots and the use cases are clarified and exploration of RabbitMQ technology as a Message Broker has taken place, as well as exploration of standardized protocols (OPC-UA, IEC 62714, IEC 62264). Designing of RESTful Web APIs and implementation of RESTful APIs with ASP.NET Core 3 has already started. Designing the Communication Interfaces for interconnection with MES, RSC, DSS and New iLike Machine Platform is taking place, as well as setting up of the HLCM.
Required input
Simulated data from the machine sensors to the Machine Level Communication Middleware (New iLike Machine Platform), as well as tracked KPIs, production times, starts and stops from MES / ERP systems. Development of the algorithms based on s/w components MES/ERP data needs of each end user.
Delivery Estimation
A Minimum Viable Product (MVP) will be delivered to the end users by M25. From their feedback we will proceed on fixing defects, enriching current features or implementing several new features. System integration with the rest of the iQonic system will be concluded until M29. At the end of M31 HLCM should be ready to be delivered to the end users for final testing and evaluation. Taking into account the given feedback a further refinement of the system will be made, in order to reach the final version of the component by the end of M33.

Table 3-8: A data modelling platform capable of real-time operation that exhibits optimal performance and system stability (BRUNEL)

Technology Description
The data modelling platform provides an analytical synopsis of severity of defect and the recyclability/reusability scores the production material in the iQonic manufacturing system. Its main functionality is to acquire the necessary information from the manufacturing and assembly process, diagnose the causal relations of defect generation, and effectively provide a prognosis of the state of the system. The prognosis will lead to improved optimisation of the process chain operations and defect management based on strategies for improving defect life--cycle management, user recommendations including risk mitigating actions on identified defects.
Status
Assembly data from PRIMA has been analysed and a flowchart about the assembly process has been built. An Arena simulation model has been established to supply us with a straightforward idea about the manufacturing and assembly process. Also, the weight of each sub-process in affecting the final defect/non-defect ratio has been explained and final product quality has been provided based on the strategies, incoming data and predictions. For the sub-processes that exert most influence on the final quality of the product, the associate inputs and outputs have been clarified. The correlations among these inputs, outputs and KPIs have been explored with a view to developing possible suggestions/recommendations for defect detection and strategy actions. The output indicates the performance and the improvement of the suggestions and recommendations of the data modelling platform.
Required input
All data from PRIMA and ficonTEC; Live sensorial data; historical data from various external systems; alarms from other iQonic sub-systems; predictions for the defect detection and severity; predictions from data analysis sub-components; KRIs which compute the risk mitigation actions; recommendations feedback; KPIs feedback
Delivery Estimation
The first version of the software platform will be ready (tested) on M23 and will be deployed for our end-users till M25. The integration of the “smart” tag and the visual inspection sub systems will be on M26. Accounting for the possible feedbacks, a further refinement of the platform will be executed, and the final version is envisioned by the end of M29.

Table 3-9: Early malfunction detection and prediction inference engine (CORE)

Technology Description
The early malfunction detection and prediction inference engine is a real time dynamic component that detects deviations from normal operation of the machine and forecasts future machine states with respect to product quality.
Status
The initial modelling and data analytics have begun for the PRIMA use case. Effort is ongoing to assess each individual system measurement with respect to the process KPIs (PRIMArily Fiber Lens Power). Also, Anomaly Detection Autoencoders are in design phase.
Required input
Engine requires the following inputs: machine settings, sensor values, product quality characteristics, start/stop actions, maintenance reports, product quality reports and manufacturing scheduling.
Delivery Estimation
An early prototype will be ready after M32, since its deployment requires the data gathering and communication systems to be fully operational. Data have to be collecting after this process in order to separate machine states according to expert knowledge and model the “normal” working regime of the machine (defect-free state). This also has to be interfaced with the communication systems to return its output in real time for downstream consumption.

Table 3-10: CPS for defects evaluation for reuse-qualification of products (POLIMI)

Technology Description
Methodology, software tool and hardware implementation of a system for avoiding the propagation of defects in multi-stage opto-electronics process chains by adapting the downstream process settings depending on the quality characteristics of the components processed at upstream stages, observed by in-line inspection. The system can represent an important technological enabler for sustainable manufacturing, making it possible to convert an otherwise wasted component into a regenerated and reusable product.
Status
The architecture of a Cyber-Physical System has been defined and the detailed input/output description of the composing building blocks have been formalized. The target application cases within the iQonic use-cases have been formulated, resulting into six different instances of the CPSs for the PRIMA, ALPES, FILAR, FILAR-HiLase thin-disk and BRIGHTERWAVE use cases. The development of the underlying process metal-models is starting.
Required input
Online measurements for the characterization of the quality of the components process at the upstream stages of the process-chain. Nominal product information in terms of expected deviation root causes, product structure and existing type of joints. Target KPIs of the assembled product. Sample production data to validate the approach.
Estimation of delivery
The CPSs for the different use-cases will be delivered throughout the life of WP5, with final delivery estimated at month M29.

Table 3-11: Modular grasping hardware supporting a range of production assembly and tuning tasks (SHADOW)

Technology Description
Robot end-of-arm-tooling hardware supporting FILAR use case with intelligent capabilities (Improved hardware and software systems allowing better robotic grasping and interaction with manufacturing tasks).
Status
Requirements for the FILAR crystal rod grinding task has been broken down into subtasks (e.g. grasp control, grasp quality, grasp stabilization, impedance control & learning by demonstration) and will be executed with teleoperation to explore how the system will work as a feasibility study and then automate the process. General improvements have been made on the robustness of the grasping hardware and the systems health report checks. A new enhanced driver has been integrated to increase accuracy, performance and allow for faster recovery in case of failure.
Required input
The system will require the position and orientation of the crystal rod in meters with respect to the robot system. The pose of the grinding wheel is also required as an input to know the placing location of the rod. Finally, an input defining the completion of the grinding process will be needed. This might be defined via experiments (e.g. time of operation). The required force to perform the grinding will be required to the controller, this might be defined via experiments. Final positioning of the ground rod will be required to complete the operation. All position and orientations must be provided to the system via ROS msgs.
Delivery Estimation
We will run the demo at our lab mimicking the crystal rod grinding task at the end of M24 as a proof of concept it will not be a deployable system. Although, we understand that we could take the demo to other partners if it is working well.

Table 3-12: New iLike Machine Platform functionalities (HOLONIX)

Technology Description
iLike Machines represents one of the main interoperability elements in iQonic platform, providing a messaging layer enabling the communication both with the field and among the other upper modules of iQonic. It is composed of two main elements: Machine Level Communication Middleware (i.e. a “Field to Cloud” layer of the IoT stack) and Rabbit MQ (messaging system based on AMQP, enabling a publishing / subscribing mechanism and checking how messages are structured and written).
Status
Current set of requirements from the use cases (with particular focus on PRIMA ones) has led to the definition of the architecture and to the new functionalities / features: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multitenancy: a tenant defines an isolated environment dedicated to a customer, partner or a project • Type of communication: direct mode and delegated mode • Device types: logical grouping of devices that share common traits, typically they map to types of equipment. Devices are instances of a given device type • Data series and schemas, for the definition of message types that will be exchanged • MQTT communication channel A first deployment supporting PRIMA use case is up and running on a cloud server.
Required input
Input: full definition of the use case requirements, including the specifications required by iQonic partners leading the development of the upper layers modules. A full development and testing of all the new functionalities will follow, also according to needs coming from the field.
Delivery Estimation
The first version of the prototype is up and running (M18) on a cloud server, testing and integration within iQonic platform are on-going and consolidate prototype will be deployed for end-users till M29, reaching a second version prior to WP7 validations.

Table 3-13: Knowledge Based System (HOLONIX)

Technology Description
The Knowledge Based System (KBS) has been developed as component of iLike Machines (ILM) platform proposed by HOLONIX aiming at providing an advanced management of huge quantities of data in the field of machinery management. The systems provides a robust layer for long term sensor data storage, whose typical use case scenarios are related to the access to data for verifications (e.g. in case of tracking down some issue) and to the retrieval of data in batches (e.g. for training the reasoning components and, when required, feeding the high level components of iQonic).
Status
KBS includes three main key features, respectively related to <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • data storage: it is designed to handle large amounts of data across many commodity servers, providing high availability with no single point of failure • data ingestion: it gets sensor data (format compliant with predefined schemas) from a topic of the Machine level communication middleware, merges them with the other domain / context information and then writes the enriched data into db. • data retrieval: it consists of web services and endpoints (access to the data wrapped with a HTTP API exposed by this element of the KBS) A first instance is included in iLike Machines platform deployed for PRIMA use case.
Required input
Full definition of the use case requirements, including the specifications required by iQonic partners leading the development of the upper layers modules. A full development and testing of all the features will follow, also according to needs coming from the field.
Delivery Estimation
The first version of the prototype is included into iLike Machines instance deployed on a cloud server (M18). Full development, testing and integration within iQonic platform are on-going. Consolidate prototype will be deployed for end-users until M29, reaching a second version prior to WP7 validations.

Table 3-14: New functionalities of Integra Traceability Kit Product (SENSAP)

Technology Description
Increase the Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) by eliminating defects products and reduce the set-up time of the production machine through a "smart" tagging process. Multi-sensorial data acquisition unit with enhanced functionality/processing and interconnectivity.
Status
<p>The enhanced multi-sensorial data acquisition unit is in its final development phase. Additional communication protocols and data schemes were adopted and communication among iQonic devices and iLike platform from Holonix was achieved and is currently in testing phase.</p> <p>The "smart" tagging process is under development focusing on the set of data needed to characterise the product status, phase and related manufacturing step/process in the production chain of each demo case it will be utilized. We need to define the best fit tag technology for the opto-electronics components as they have a footprint size at (sub-)mm scale. A first study regarding ALPES and PRIMA demo cases is underway and tag samples from our suppliers are expected.</p> <p>The detection of defect products as an outcome of the visual inspection module is currently under investigation with a data set from PRIMA end-user.</p>
Required input
<p>Shadow robot communication and the integration of the new additional sensors needs to be completed. The sensors have been identified and are currently in the integration phase. The communication with the Shadow robot is defined and it will be implemented by M18 using a virtual twin.</p> <p>In addition, visual inspection data needs to be acquired and integrated into the communication data flow. The data models (structure) depicted by WP2 and WP3 needs to be analysed and validated.</p>
Delivery Estimation
The first version of the prototype will be ready (tested) on M17 and will be deployed for our end-users till M20, reaching a second version prior to WP7. The integration of the "smart" tag and the visual inspection sub systems will be on M26.

Table 3-15: Laser thin-disk head (HiLase/IP-ASCR)

Technology Description
Machine for precise bonding of thin-disk is designed as sample handling tool which will help avoiding damage and bending of the thin-disk sample (process chain development and optimization of thin-disk bonding to the heat sink).
Status
Currently working on having the uniform layer of epoxy with no voids and bubbles, while evaluating samples (trying to find some correlation with temperature, way the epoxy is delivered, etc.). Looking into and investigating all process steps trying to clarify and obtain the lamda/10 surface parallelism after bonding.
Required input
All data from FiconTEC machine.
Delivery Estimation
We foresee existing machine with just additional monitoring of certain parameters will give excellent and reliable results and all delivery estimation we will be able in May or June 2020.

Table 3-16: Inspection systems that based on adaptive optics (FORTH)

Technology Description
Optical identification and characterization of critical defects (<i>i.e. in ALPES use case</i>) not visible by regular microscopy imaging. The adaptive in-line optical system could provide real-time feedback in the process flow and in the in-chain inspection of the materials assembly and manufacturing parameters.
Status
The developed optical apparatus is based on a modified fully-motorized microscope with excitation source a fs-laser. The laser beam is passing through a pair of galvanometric mirrors, which are moving accordingly to create a raster-scanning scheme. The optical resolution accomplished by the system is in the sub-micron scale (~700nm radial and ~1100nm axial resolutions). Depending on the scanning speed the pixel size is defined. The wide-field channel of the CCD-detector is equipped with digitally adaptive z-correction module. Several imaging tests in order to adjust the optical parameters are performed in defected samples provided by ALPES.
Required input
The definition, identification and verification of the critical defects in hard-mask adhesion process in ALPES wafers use case.
Delivery Estimation
We will run a demo, at our lab, of the optical inspection system performing evaluation of thin film quality at the end of M24.

Table 3-17: Flexible high precision assembly system with increased yield (FICONTEC)

Technology Description
Increase the OEE by eliminating defective products and reduce the set-up time of the production machine through a "smart" tagging process. Multi-sensorial data acquisition unit with enhanced functionality/processing and interconnectivity.
Status
The assembly machine dedicated for the experiments is completely assembled and will be transferred to the R&D labs mid of March. As soon as the machine is setup the assembly process will be developed. This process must be adopted to the special needs for data saving required to give the required input data to the project partners for data analysis and prediction.
Required input
Feedback from project partners and decision support system about possible future failure mechanisms.
Delivery Estimation
Data acquisition and transfer to partners ready by July 2020

Table 3-18: Olfactory system for detecting contamination (SACMI)

Technology Description
Electronic olfactory system capable to detect the presence of contaminant organic molecules in the materials used in the assembly. The product is integrated in a quality inspection automated system.
Status
One electronic olfactory system is under testing for detection and quantification of epoxy. Remote data communication with Sensap has been successfully established through an XML webservice, where the user can read the output of the measurement in terms of classification, quantification and duration of the odour under study. New electronic components are under development due to the phase-out of current technology (CPU module), that requires an upgrade of the operating system and the HMI software; a working prototype is currently under trial.

Required input
The system requires input from the user to set up and start/stop the measurement. This input can be given locally using the display or through remote control of the machine (Pocket Controller software in current systems, while in new instruments the remote-control software has to be defined after the upgrading of the operating system).
Delivery Estimation
A first demonstrator system is ready for local testing of detection and data communication. Three prototypes will be ready for delivery to the end users on M24 for integration and evaluation.

Table 3-19: Active and passive component bonding processes in micro-optics (TAU)

Technology Description
The iQonic technology component includes the development of active and passive micro-optic component bonding processes targeting for zero-defect manufacturing. The technology component defines modular bonding process chains for different component types with varying special requirements enabling flexibility, excellent performance, and high reliability in micro-optic component bonding with relatively low costs.
Status
In iQonic at least two bonding processes are considered 1) UV-adhesive bonding and 2) soldering. The key performance indicators of the main two bonding processes, employed in iQonic, are identified. The generic frameworks of the main bonding processes are defined. Subsequently, critical process parameters are identified. The effect of these process parameters to KPIs are investigated from theoretical point of view. Different options to carry out reverse bonding processes and possible disassembly are considered. Since conventional UV-bonding and eutectic soldering are not very practical in applications in which components must be disassembled, other bonding techniques, including mechanical bonding and thermally curable adhesives, are also examined.
Required input
The technology component requires inputs from end users in order to define the KPIs and align these requirements with the process chain model. The activity also requires the component, handling tool, assembly system, and characterization system specifications, opto-thermo-electro-mechanical design, and environmental parameters in order to adjust the modular bonding process chain with requirements. The bonding processes also need feedback to adjust the bonding parameters.
Delivery Estimation
Different hardware providers can locally test the technology component before M25. The technology component will be integrated and tested with the iQonic solution in WP7 (M25-M29). Based on the feedback given by hardware providers and end users, the technology component will be updated during M31-M33.

4 Demo Cases scenarios adaptation and system operational environment

The project is dealing with optoelectronics and overall process chain optimisation. Specifically, iQonic will namely handle:

- design and production of photodiodes within ALPES,
- assembly of medium sized lasers for manufacturing in PRIMA,
- design and development of optical amplifiers and crystals in FILAR and
- miniaturized lasers for augmented reality - BRIGHTERWAVE.

This section describes the initial plan on adaptation of iQonic at Demo Case level and system operational environment. A brief overview of the Demo Case scenarios at the pilots is presented at Table 4-20.

Table 4-20: List of iQonic Demo Case Scenarios and Use Cases

<i>Demo Case</i>	<i>Scenario</i>	<i>Use Case (UC)</i>
	Defect categorization, management and yield increase in high variant production	<i>UC-AL-01: Front-end (defect) mapping</i>
		<i>UC-AL-02: Systematic ALT-screening</i>
		<i>UC-AL-03: Automatic COS mounting / facet inspection</i>
	High volume process chain zero-defect manufacturing	<i>UC-PR-01: Defected device screening by visual inspection</i>
		<i>UC-PR-02: Optimal adaptation and alignment of components during optical bonding</i>
	Process knowledge gathering and control for enabling new product introduction	<i>UC-FI-01: Crystal Thin Disk production</i>
		<i>UC-FI-02: Decrease defects from Ultrasonic Drilling Machine</i>
	Shortening and improving the NPI process	<i>UC-BR-01: Optimization of assembly processes for laser light sources (free-space / fiber-coupled) – alignment and bonding phases</i>

As there are many software (s/w) and hardware (h/w) components and various technologies and tools (fifteen in total) generally involved at Demo Case scenarios, the four phases of iQonic plan implementation due M20 have been defined:

- *pilot visitation* (shop floor visits of ALPES, PRIMA, FILAR, BRIGHTERWAVE),
- *preparatory* (quality product characterization, defects classifications, definition of software and hardware components' and Demo Case requirements, etc.),
- *development* (design of s/w and h/w components and their generic architecture, preliminary validation of modules with collected and IoT data) and
- *deployment* (initial implementation and deployment of /w and h/w components within pilots).

This plan is based first on visitation of the pilots' shop floors and interaction with technicians and future End Users of iQonic solution gathering a wide range of information regarding the shop floor processes as well as the products themselves. During the first few months both s/w and h/w component developers are familiarised with the areas of the Demo Case scenarios getting aware on the Use Cases where the components are to be deployed focusing on different perspectives while continuously engaging with End Users. Following, the s/w and h/w component developers went deeper into understanding and analysing the quality characterization of the products, classifying the defect type and severity, occurrence and impact on involved process chain and production stage. Also, the definition, refinement and validation of s/w and h/w components requirements took place providing the base for component design. Note must be made that when a certain phase started, at least one of the s/w and/or h/w components were available for development, test, implementation, deployment and/or operation at one of the Demo Case scenarios. Consequently, the actual operation of each scenario will be achieved gradually. This report (M20) is related to the monitoring of the very initial implementation at Demo Case Scenarios, whereas the entire integrated scenario operation as well as full component deployment will be documented at *D7.4 Report on iQonic Solution Validation through Demonstration* (M40). Thus, the Figure 4-20 covers only the activities performed due M20 of the projects life which will be revisited (in the future) for the components that are not available for adaptation at this phase of the project. Following this concept as well as based on the consortium results obtained due M20, the details of s/w and h/w components involvement per Demo Use Case are presented at Table 4-21. Note must be made that some of the components are still in the conceptual phase that does not necessary mean that their current status of adaptation will not be clarified further on as the project matures.

Consequently, based on the pre-knowledge from previous projects and in communication with the consortium the preliminary plan is initially defined. It was foreseen that specific dates will change as deployment and Demo Use Case scenarios are further progressing and end Use Cases being further refined. The final s/w and h/w component versions will be setup at the pilot partners (WP8).

Table 4-21: Gantt diagram of the implementation phases of the Demo Case scenarios at iQonic

		Implementation phases	M01	M02	M03	M04	M05	M06	M07	M08	M09	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	
Demo Cases	<i>Pilot Visitation</i>																						
	<i>Preparatory</i>																						
	<i>*Development</i>																						
	<i>*Deployment</i>																						

* will be further continued in the following twenty months

Table 4-22: Adaptation of s/w and h/w components per Demo Case

s/w & h/w component developers	ALPES	PRIMA	FILAR	BRIGHERWAVE
- FRAUNHOFER - <i>Process chain optimised designs for micro-macro assembly and disassembly</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y
- ATLANTIS - <i>Defect Severity Decision Support System</i>	TBD	Y	TBD	TBD
- ATLANTIS - <i>Reverse Supply Chain Process Strategy</i>	TBD	Y	TBD	N
- ATLANTIS - <i>Higher Level Communication Middleware</i>	Y	Y	TBD	N
- BRUNEL- <i>A data modelling platform capable of real-time operation that exhibits optimal performance and system stability</i>	TBD	Y	Y	TBD
- CORE – <i>Early malfunction detection and prediction inference engine</i>	TBD	Y	TBD	N
- POLIMI - <i>CPS for defects evaluation for reuse- requalification of products</i>	Y	Y	Y	N
- SHADOW – <i>Modular grasping hardware supporting a range of production assembly and tuning tasks</i>	N	N	TBD	N
- HOLONIX – <i>New iLike Machine Platform functionalities</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y
- SENSAP - <i>New functionalities of Integra Traceability Kit Product</i>	TBD	Y	Y	N
- FORTH – <i>Inspection systems that based on adaptive optics</i>	TBD	N	N	N
- FICONTEC – <i>Flexible high precision assembly system with increased yield</i>	Y	Y	N	TBD
- SACMI – <i>Olfactory system for detecting contamination</i>	Y	Y	TBD	N
- HiLase – <i>Laser thin-disk head</i>	N	N	TBD	N
- TAU –	Y	Y	Y	Y

Active and passive component bonding processes in micro-optics				
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* Y – YES, the component is adaptable in Demo Cases; *N – NO, the component is not adaptable in Demo Cases; * TBD – still in a conceptual phase. Furthermore, Fraunhofer’s contribution to the demo case “Process chain optimised designs for micro-macro assembly and disassembly” is relevant for all use cases, with the following restrictions:

- ALPES: relevant for the assembly part of the use case (not for the inspection part),
- PRIMA: relevant for the assembly part of the use case (not for the inspection part),
- FILAR: relevant for the assembly part of the use case (not for the crystal manufacturing part) and
- BRIGHTERWAVE: relevant.

4.1 ALPES

ALPES production area is split in two parts: The mounting area where laser chips are separated from wafers and mounted into various device configurations and the lab area where all the characterization of the devices is taking place. All mounting performed at this end user is done manually by operators. Figure 4-4 presents the partial overview of the end users shop floor with (1) Cleaving station, (2) Manual die bonder, (3) Facet inspection microscope, (4) Burn-in testing.

Figure 4-4: Partial overview of ALPES shop floor.

Furthermore, the overview of ALPES Pilot shop floor as well as the designated Use Case scenarios are summarised at Figure 4-5. *Adaptation of the cleaving strategy based on defect mapping information collected prior in the process flow* (UC-AL-01) concerns the device cleaving that is performed at the **cleaving station**. Cleaving is performed selectively on a part of the base material (wafer) to target devices with specific properties only. The use case consists in optimising the cleaving strategy by taking into account aggregated data on defects identified on the wafer in order to minimize number of samples to be cleaved and mounted.

Furthermore, *Early detection of failure mechanisms affecting device lifetime* (UC-AL-02) deals with early detection of defects that affect the lifetime of the devices by accelerated lifetime testing (ALT). These defects cannot be found by visual inspection. The ALT measurement station will be constructed next to our burn-in station that is shown in the pictures above and is situated in the lab area.

Finally, *Mounting chips automatically in ficonTEC micro-optics assembly station (in their facility) and optionally inspect the device facet for geometric measurements to be fed back into analysis* (UC-AL-03) consists in out-sourcing part of the mounting to ficonTEC in order to be able to use the machine that they are going to build for the iQonic project. The steps that are done manually at ALPES and that are going to be performed at ficonTEC is the die-bonding where a laser chip is soldered onto a sub-mount and the subsequent

facet inspection step (optionally, if their system will be equipped with a camera system with sufficient magnification).

Figure 4-5: Overview of ALPES Pilot shop floor and designated Use Case scenarios

4.2 FILAR

FILAR Optomaterials's shop floor consists in 1500 ms q facility. It building hosts administration offices while the shop floor is divided into three facilities: optical characterization and quality control of the crystals, optomechanical department and finally crystal growth department. Figure 4-6 presents partial overview of FILAR shop floor with (1) Ultrasonic drilling station into optomechanical area; (2) Laser marking station into optomechanical area and (3) Lapping and polishing stations into optomechanical area.

Figure 4-6: Partial overview of FILAR shop floor

Red area of the Figure 4-7, presents the two use cases that take place in the FILAR Pilot shop floor where *Crystal Thin Disk production* (UC-FI-01) is dealing with challenge to obtain Crystal thin Disk to satisfy partners requirement in laser Disk application while *Decrease defects from Ultrasonic Drilling Machine* (UC-FI-02) is working on a challenge to improve the working features of the Ultrasonic drilling machine; fundamental machinery employed to drill crystal rods from crystal bulk material (boule).

Figure 4-7: Overview of FILAR Pilot shop floor and designated Use Case scenarios

4.3 PRIMA

The Torino Diode Fab of PRIMA electro is producing high power multi-emitter diodes laser modules for industrial application, mainly as pump source for PRIMA Electro fiber lasers. The process flow, end its implementation in the shop floor, can be simplified in the following steps:

- design of the epitaxial structures and diode laser,
- wafer processing in the Torino laboratories,
- wafer scribing, bars coating and testing,
- bars dicing and visual inspection,
- Chip on Carrier (CoC) assembly,
- CoC testing and Burn In screening and final visual inspection,
- package assembly and optical alignment,
- module testing, shake down,
- final delivery of good parts.

Figure 4-8 presents the partial view of the PRIMA shop floor (back end cleanroom): 1) bars automatic cleaving; 2) manual visual inspection; 3) Chip on Carrier loading on trays for Testing and Burn-In; 4) automatic optical alignment steps using FiconTEC machine.

Figure 4-8: Partial overview of *PRIMA* shop floor

Figure 4-9: Overview of *PRIMA* Pilot shop floor and designated Use Case scenarios

Figure 4-9, presents the use cases that take place in the Die Fab area (left) and in the Packaging Area (right). Consequently, the *Diode laser process flow* include screening stage through morphology inspection at early stages, avoiding propagation in the final stage of the product line of maverick parts (*UC-PR-01*) use case is focused on step 6), which is requiring a time consuming visual inspection on the CoC after Burn In for a final rejection of failed parts. This step is also influenced by operator judgment and therefore a constant output

quality is difficult to maintain. Image recognition and defect detection algorithms developed during the project will significantly improve the cycle time and the output quality of this crucial step. Finally, *Multi-emitter diode laser package requires active alignment of optics which is a crucial step in terms of device performance, yield and lead time* (UC-PR-02) use case is focused on step 7), which active alignment of module micro-optics is strongly affecting product cycle time and device performances. Improved algorithms implemented in the project will significantly improve the cycle time and the repeatability if the overall performances.

4.4 BRIGHTERWAVE

The BRIGHTERWAVE's laboratory acts as a Research and Development (R&D) centre and quality control of the products aiming to improve the assembly of optoelectronics multi-component modulus requiring high precision and reliability. The actual laser module assembly work is partly done in collaboration with Tampere University at their shop floor and partly at facilities of BRIGHTERWAVE's manufacturing partners.

Figure 4-10: Partial overview of *BRIGHTERWAVE* shop floor.

Figure 4-10 presents the partial overview of the shop floor of this end users and the deployment of the *Optimization of assembly processes for laser light sources (free-space / fiber-coupled) – alignment and bonding phases* (UC-BR-01) use case (Figure 4-11) where BRIGHTERWAVE's laboratory is inspecting, measuring and characterizing the laser components and laser modules checking the quality control of the products.

Figure 4-11: Overview of *BRIGHTERWAVE* Pilot shop floor and designated Use Case scenario

5 Small scale iQonic demo sample holder

As the project evolved, it appeared that technology providing partner HiLase, also became a partial small-scale end users and simple demo holder of iQonic system. Based on this outcome, the business case of HiLase is summarised and presented in section 5.1. Further development and obtained results will be presented in various WPs (e.g. WP6) due end of the project life time (M42).

5.1 HiLase

HiLase is R&D center focused on design and development of diode pump solid state laser systems. One of technology in use is based on so call thin-disk. As a part of this technology, a purchased rod of laser material with predefine specifications is used for production of a thin disk head trough following production steps:

- Cutting of material to thin disks.
- Polishing and cleaning.
- Coating with HR and AR materials (outside of HiLase).
- Bonding to the heat sink material .
- Optical testing.

Despite HiLase has all required equipment, often even cutting, polishing and cleaning is done by the crystal producer. While number of produced items is relatively small, all processes of *DSC-HI-01: Thin-disk module bonding* including final inspection before implementing in a laser system, are done in HiLase optical workshop (“pilot shop floor”)

Figure 5-12: Thin disk head (left), thin disk laser material bonded on heat sink (middle) and surface profile of bonded crystal $PV=54.1$ nm, $R=1011$ m, $R_x=5222$ m, $R_y=559.6$ m)

6 Conclusion and next steps

Monitoring of vertical development of iQonic s/w and h/w component level, horizontal process chain implementation level as well as tracking of their adaptation at ALPES, PRIMA, FILAR and BRIGHTERWAVE Pilot Demo Cases is the objective of this task T2.5. First, the activities related with overall approach, methodology and initial conception of iQonic strategies, their correlation with s/w and h/w components (exploitable results), Technical Objectives as well as milestones have been reported, reviewed and applied. Parallely, it was recognised that the Quality management systems standard and data collection principles (ISO standards) in general provide the tangible aid and measurable benefit to almost every possible sector supporting the technology that we depend on, guaranteeing the expected quality. Furthermore, Requirements have been revised through two iteration periods (II and III) i.e., two requirement quality reassessments and reported in the ANNEX of this deliverable. Finally, the development of the tasks within the WP3-WP6 work packages took place, where the deliverable *D2.5 Strategy implementation report* as a public file summarises the very first and draft means for process validation and adaptation as well as the progress that is monitored due M20 aligned with the activities outlined in Sections 3 and 4 of this document. Note must be made, during the evolvement of the project, it was clear that HiLase, besides being the technical providing partner, also developed their own business case and it will be considered as a small scale iQonic demo sample holder during the lifetime of the project. Further on, this draft plan will be revised, completed and finalised throughout the tasks *T7.2 Technology Validation* and *T7.3 Solution Validation through demonstration* while the iQonic technologies will be tested in relevant Pilot and working environments (WP8).

ANNEX I

At the beginning of the project the requirement methodology for collection of iQonic requirements has been defined. Following the methodology, during the first few months of the project, consortium requirements according to their business and/or manufacturing processes, technical and non-technical needs, wishes and constraints have been reported and summarised in *D2.1 User Requirements* deliverable. The two requirement quality checks (iteration II and III) were applied due M20 respectfully in order for partners to:

- revise and refine requirements and report any other new once that came up during the component development phase, providing directions on which requirements could be included in the system implementation (iteration II),
- finally validate the requirements through various techniques of testing, prototyping, etc., for the ultimate quality check enhancing the fit criteria, expectations, dependences, etc., (iteration III).

During the II iteration and quality check, the consortium partners HOLONIX, FRAUNHOFER, CORE, TAU, FORTH, HILASE and POLIMI have revised the originally reported requirements (RQs) of iteration I. It was concluded that those RQs are still valid and no new needs have been reported at the time. Furthermore, the RQ quality check was completed by SENSAP that reported two new needs while both FICONTEC and SHADOW defined five new requirements in this period of requirement quality check. Also, SACMI stated that two requirements were not valid, BRUNEL proposed to deleted on requirement that was duplicated while ATLANTIS closed three requirements at the time of the 1st quality assessment.

During the III iteration and quality check, all partners have revised their RQs and this Annex I present the ultimate summary and details of final and 2nd requirements quality assessment obtained during the M19/M20. Corresponding details have been provided with the sub-sections below.

HOLONIX

Minor modifications have been provided to HO-T-03 and HO-T-07 requirements. In particular, according to the structure of the document, the RQs will be kept tracked while indicating that are rejected. In parallel, two new RQs were added as new (HO-T-03-2 and HO-T-07-2).

KBS – Production process

RQ ID	HO-T-01		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	NO	<i>Agreed</i>	NO	<i>Baselined</i>	NO	<i>Rejected</i>	NO			
Parent RQ	N/A										
Title (Summary)	The Knowledge Base System (KBS) shall store the whole information related to production processes, assets and products.										
Rationale (why, what, how)	KBS shall guarantee a coherent storage and persistency of the whole information in order to allow proper data retrieval enabling correlation between the different pieces, e.g. production stage – process parameters - defect generation. A specific DB will be developed on this purpose.										
Reporter	HOLONIX				Assignee			FRAUNHOFER			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	Analysis and full definition of the requirements of the use case, so that related information is known.										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Big-data storing capabilities, CRUD operations										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	N/A										
Component/s	Knowledge based system (KBS)										
Date (change history)	20.12.2018; 04/03/2020; 30/04/2020										

RQ ID	HO-T-02	RQ Type			Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE
Status	<i>New</i>	NO	<i>Agreed</i>	NO	<i>Baselined</i>	NO	<i>Rejected</i>	NO	
Parent RQ	HO-T-01								
Title (Summary)	The Knowledge Base System (KBS) shall store information according to a proper data schema in order to be easily accessible by the users								
Rationale (why, what, how)	KBS shall make use of a data schema to optimize the accessibility of information and the easiness of data retrieval by the users.								
Reporter	HOLONIX				Assignee			FRAUNHOFER	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Agreement with partners about the expected structure of the information to be stored and exposed								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Big-data storing capabilities, handling large data sets and operates at massive scale, easy and fast data retrieval functional to a possible commercial exploitation								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	HO-T-01								
Component/s	Knowledge based system (KBS), New iLike Machine Platform functionalities								
Date (change history)	20.12.2018; 04/03/2020; 30/04/2020								

RQ ID	HO-T-03	RQ Type			Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE
Status	<i>New</i>	NO	<i>Agreed</i>	NO	<i>Baselined</i>	NO	<i>Rejected</i>	YES	
Parent RQ	HO-T-01								
Title (Summary)	The Knowledge Base System (KBS) shall enable the transformation raw data from the shopfloor to be stored according to the iQonic semantic model								
Rationale (why, what, how)	KBS shall use a component (RDFizer) to transform raw data from sensors/machines and company's ERP/MES into data structures suitable to be stored in the DB.								
Reporter	HOLONIX				Assignee			FRAUNHOFER	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions									
Acceptance/Fit Criteria									
Exceptions									
Dependencies									
Component/s									
Date (change history)	20.12.2018; 04/03/2020; 30/04/2020								

RQ ID	HO-T-03-2		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	YES	<i>Agreed</i>	NO	<i>Baselined</i>	NO	<i>Rejected</i>	NO			
Parent RQ	HO-T-01, HO-T-02										
Title (Summary)	The Knowledge Base System (KBS) shall enable the transformation raw data from the shopfloor to be stored according to a defined data schema										
Rationale (why, what, how)	KBS shall use possible components to preprocess raw data from sensors/machines and company's ERP/MES into data structures suitable to be stored in the DB.										
Reporter	HOLONIX				Reporter			HOLONIX			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Priority	
Pre-conditions	Full specifications regarding the required information and its content										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Making available information with expected format and content after possible pre-processing										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	HO-T-02										
Component/s	Knowledge based system (KBS), New iLike Machine Platform functionalities										
Date (change history)	20.12.2018; 04/03/2020; 30/04/2020										

RQ ID	HO-T-04		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	NO	<i>Agreed</i>	NO	<i>Baselined</i>	NO	<i>Rejected</i>	NO			
Parent RQ	HO-T-01										
Title (Summary)	The Knowledge Base System (KBS) shall allow inference to make correlation between defects and process parameters										
Rationale (why, what, how)	KBS shall help users to reduce/eliminate defects enabling the development of a reasoner that will make correlation between products defects and process parameters										
Reporter	HOLONIX				Assignee			FRAUNHOFER			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	Info provided by partners: i) full knowledge concerning the process; ii) analysis and classification of defects; iii) definition of the roles and relationships between process and product										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Making available information which allows: i) recognitions and reduction of defects; ii) process optimization; iii) provides faster and better decisions										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	HO-T-01, HO-T-02										
Component/s	Knowledge based system (KBS)										
Date (change history)	20.12.2018; 04/03/2020; 30/04/2020										

KBS – Products reuse/requalification

RQ ID	HO-T-05	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	NO	<i>Agreed</i>	NO	<i>Baselined</i>	NO	<i>Rejected</i>	NO	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	The Knowledge Base System (KBS) shall store the whole information related to product defects and technologies and tools for products reuse and requalification.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	KBS shall guarantee a coherent storage and persistency of the whole information in order to allow proper data retrieval enabling correlation between the different pieces, e.g.: defective product – technology to be applied – assets and tools. Data will be stored according to a defined structure.								
Reporter	HOLONIX			Assignee			POLIMI		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Analysis and full definition of the requirements of the use case, so that related information is known.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Big-data storing capabilities, CRUD operations								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	N/A								
Component/s	Knowledge based system (KBS)								
Date (change history)	20.12.2018; 04/03/2020; 30/04/2020								

RQ ID	HO-T-06	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	NO	<i>Agreed</i>	NO	<i>Baselined</i>	NO	<i>Rejected</i>	NO	
Parent RQ	HO-T-05								
Title (Summary)	The Knowledge Base System (KBS) shall store information according to a proper data schema in order to be easily accessible by the users								
Rationale (why, what, how)	KBS shall make use of a data schema to optimize the accessibility of information and the easiness of data retrieval by the users.								
Reporter	HOLONIX			Assignee			POLIMI		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Agreement with partners about the expected structure of the information to be stored and exposed								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Big-data storing capabilities, handling large data sets and operates at massive scale, easy and fast data retrieval functional to a possible commercial exploitation								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	HO-T-05								
Component/s	Knowledge based system (KBS), New iLike Machine Platform functionalities								
Date (change history)	20.12.2018; 04/03/2020; 30/04/2020								

RQ ID	HO-T-07		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	NO	<i>Agreed</i>	NO	<i>Baselined</i>	NO	<i>Rejected</i>	YES			
Parent RQ	HO-T-05										
Title (Summary)	The Knowledge Base System (KBS) shall enable the transformation of raw data from the shopfloor to be stored according to the iQonic semantic model										
Rationale (why, what, how)	KBS shall use a component (RDFizer) to transform raw data from sensors used for quality control and information related to reuse and requalification technologies into data structures suitable to be stored in the DB										
Reporter	HOLONIX				Assignee			POLIMI			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions											
Acceptance/Fit Criteria											
Exceptions											
Dependencies											
Component/s											
Date (change history)	20.12.2018; 04/03/2020; 30/04/2020										

RQ ID	HO-T-07-2		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	YES	<i>Agreed</i>	NO	<i>Baselined</i>	NO	<i>Rejected</i>	NO			
Parent RQ	HO-T-05										
Title (Summary)	The Knowledge Base System (KBS) shall enable the transformation raw data from the shopfloor to be stored according to a defined data schema										
Rationale (why, what, how)	KBS shall use possible components to preprocess raw data from sensors/machines and company's ERP/MES into data structures suitable to be stored in the DB										
Reporter	HOLONIX				Reporter			HOLONIX			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Priority	
Pre-conditions	Full specifications regarding the required information and its content										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Making available information with expected format and content after possible pre-processing										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	HO-T-06										
Component/s	Knowledge based system (KBS), New iLike Machine Platform functionalities										
Date (change history)	20.12.2018; 04/03/2020; 30/04/2020										

RQ ID	HO-T-08		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	NO	<i>Agreed</i>	NO	<i>Baselined</i>	NO	<i>Rejected</i>	NO			
Parent RQ	HO-T-05										
Title (Summary)	The Knowledge Base System (KBS) shall allow inference to make correlation between defective products and reuse/requalification technologies										
Rationale (why, what, how)	KBS shall help users to reduce/eliminate scraps enabling the development of a reasoner that will make correlation between defective products, technology to be applied to reuse/requalify them and tool/assets required.										
Reporter	HOLONIX				Assignee			POLIMI			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	Info provided by partners: i) full knowledge concerning the technologies; ii) analysis and classification of defects of products; iii) definition of the roles and relationships between defective products and reuse/requalification technologies										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Making available information which allows: i) recognitions and reduction of defects; ii) technologies; iii) provides faster and better decisions										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	HO-T-05, HO-T-06										
Component/s	Knowledge based system (KBS)										
Date (change history)	20.12.2018; 04/03/2020; 30/04/2020										

ATLANTIS

Decision Support System

RQ ID	AT-T-01		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	N/A										
Title (Summary)	The higher-level Decision Support System (DSS) shall respond to the defects and their severity.										
Rationale (why, what, how)	The higher-level Decision Support System (DSS) shall enable optimum response to other recommendations in order to minimize defects and their severity.										
Reporter	ATLANTIS				Assignee			ATLANTIS			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	Analysis and classification of defects by appropriate technical provider (e.g. CORE).										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	DSS generates recommendations to inform end users to take appropriate actions										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	AT-T-02, AT-T-03, AT-T-04, AT-T-05, AT-T-06										
Component/s	Higher Level Communication Middleware										
Date (change history)	23.11.2018; 10.09.2019; 10.04.2020										

RQ ID	AT-T-02		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	AT-T-01										
Title (Summary)	The DSS shall analyse the defect types from all use cases.										
Rationale (why, what, how)	Analysis of common causes of defects and production of classifications by DSS in terms of defect severity, occurrence and impact on involved process chain and production.										
Reporter	ATLANTIS				Assignee			ATLANTIS			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	Common causes of defect types should be defined by the end users										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Categorization of defects by DSS into different groups per use case in terms of severity, occurrence and impact on involved process chain and production.										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	AT-T-01										
Component/s	Higher Level Communication Middleware										
Date (change history)	23.11.2018; 10.09.2019; 10.04.2020										

RQ ID	AT-T-03		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	AT-T-01										
Title (Summary)	DSS shall support risk assessment based on IEC3110:2009.										
Rationale (why, what, how)	DSS shall support faster and better decision making at end users' shop-floor.										
Reporter	ATLANTIS				Assignee			ATLANTIS, ALPES, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	DSS will facilitate the adoption of risk-based thinking (in line with ISO 9001:2015).										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	DSS provides faster and better decisions while deploying risk assessment.										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	AT-T-01										
Component/s	Higher Level Communication Middleware										
Date (change history)	23.11.2018; 10.09.2019; 10.04.2020										

RQ ID	AT-T-04		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	AT-T-01										
Title (Summary)	DSS shall incorporate autonomous and hierarchical decision support with respect to provided recommendations.										
Rationale (why, what, how)	The DSS is to provide recommendations for optimum response to defects.										
Reporter	ATLANTIS				Assignee			ATLANTIS			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	Recommendations will combine product monitoring models and data analytics from heterogeneous sources of monitoring-diagnosis-prediction-detection.										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The recommendations should consider optimization factors such as data uncertainty, lack of information and information quality, involvement of multiple actors, events and alarms from the diagnostic quality inspection and monitoring layers.										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	AT-T-01, AT-T-06										
Component/s	Higher Level Communication Middleware, Machine-learning element and Knowledge Base System (KBS). The KBS will store data about product, machine and process behaviors along time.										
Date (change history)	23.11.2018; 10.09.2019; 10.04.2020										

RQ ID	AT-T-05		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	AT-T-01										
Title (Summary)	DSS shall define rules and conditions to be met for each use case.										
Rationale (why, what, how)	DSS shall define semantic rules and conditions to be met for the activation of each one of the iQonic intertwined Strategies.										
Reporter	ATLANTIS				Assignee			ATLANTIS			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	Semantic rules and conditions will be defined by the end users										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	DSS will integrate a Rule-based engine for deciding the Strategy(ies) to be activated.										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	AT-T-01										
Component/s	Higher Level Communication Middleware, Rule-based engine, Cyber-Physical System (CPS). Data will be analyzed by a CPS that will generate the best strategy to regain value from defective component in-line. The CPS will act as an advanced shop-flop level feed-forward controller for preventing the propagation of defects until the end of the production line.										
Date (change history)	23.11.2018; 10.09.2019; 10.04.2020										

RQ ID	AT-T-06		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No		
Parent RQ	AT-T-01									
Title (Summary)	The DSS shall improve the efficiency of future recommendations, both for process-chain optimization and for iQonic Strategies activation.									
Rationale (why, what, how)	DSS shall store and analyse the effects and impacts from iQonic Strategies activation through its machine-learning element and provide improved future recommendations to the end user.									
Reporter	ATLANTIS				Assignee			ATLANTIS, ALPES, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No		
Pre-conditions	Integration of the machine-learning element to DSS component.									
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The machine learning system will predict quality according to each pre-selected setting having the overall performance indicator simulated to examine how they affect the final cost. The returning for optimal performance will reduce the costs by 20% and increase the yield by 22%. Therefore, achieved values close to the previously mentioned ones could be considered accepted fit criteria.									
Exceptions	N/A									
Dependencies	AT-T-01, AT-T-04									
Component/s	Higher Level Communication Middleware, Machine-learning element, Knowledge Base System (KBS).									
Date (change history)	23.11.2018; 10.09.2019; 10.04.2020									

Reverse Supply Chain

RQ ID	AT-T-07		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, PRIMA	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No		
Parent RQ	N/A									
Title (Summary)	Reverse Supply Chain (RSC) of iQonic shall understand when the defected parts/products are detected in downstream stages.									
Rationale (why, what, how)	The RSC process of iQonic will be realized when the defected products/parts are detected in downstream stages, in order to decide their possible redirection, either to upstream stages for remanufacturing or to other supply-chain tiers for possible disassembly, recycling or disposal.									
Reporter	ATLANTIS				Assignee			ATLANTIS		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No		
Pre-conditions	Integration of the CPS component to the iQonic system.									
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The new process of Reverse Supply Chain (RSC) and requalification of components at their end-of-life will aim for increased introduction of recycled and recovered parts in the production in order to reduce the material costs.									
Exceptions	N/A									
Dependencies	AT-T-08									
Component/s	Higher Level Communication Middleware, Cyberphysical System (CPS). The CPS will be used to evaluate both the functionality and integrity in order to proceed to downstream stages or upstream.									
Date (change history)	23.11.2018; 10.09.2019; 10.04.2020									

RQ ID	AT-T-08		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, PRIMA		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	AT-T-07										
Title (Summary)	The RSC shall use a rule-based engine with rules defining the conditions to be met.										
Rationale (why, what, how)	A rule-based engine will be integrated, with rules defining the conditions to be met considering the involved stages, tiers and conditions for product/part reuse and requalification. Process chain characteristics realized in each project use-case should also be considered. Semantic rules should be defined for the reverse process based on use-case input analysis.										
Reporter	ATLANTIS				Assignee			ATLANTIS			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	Integration of a Rule-based engine at the RSC component with rules defining the conditions to be met (e.g. defect severity and type, recoverable, value to recover, repairable, defect origin, stage, internal/external supply tier, etc.).										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The new process of Reverse Supply Chain (RSC) and requalification of components at their end-of-life will aim for increased introduction of recycled and recovered parts in the production in order to reduce the material costs.										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	AT-T-07										
Component/s	Higher Level Communication Middleware, Rule-based engine, KBS, CPS. The CPS will be used to evaluate both the functionality and integrity in order to proceed to downstream stages or upstream.										
Date (change history)	23.11.2018; 10.09.2019; 10.04.2020										

Higher Level Communication Middleware

RQ ID	AT-T-09		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	N/A										
Title (Summary)	Manufacturing execution systems (MES) and other higher level management systems shall communicate through Higher Level Communication Middleware application.										
Rationale (why, what, how)	Manufacturing execution systems (MES) and other higher level management systems shall exchange data, alarms about predicted/detected defects, recommendations, production and product requirements through Higher Level Communication Middleware application.										
Reporter	ATLANTIS				Assignee			ATLANTIS, HOLONIX			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	The HLC Middleware will be designed according to the standardized protocols and communication means (OPC, OPC-UA, UCMCM), based on industrial standards (e.g. IEC 62714, IEC 62264, OPC-UA).										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The relevant indicators will be activated to prove the communication among heterogeneous systems through HLC Middleware application.										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	AT-T-10										
Component/s	DSS, RSC, KBS, and other higher-level management systems e.g. ERP, MES, SCADA										
Date (change history)	23.11.2018; 10.09.2019; 10.04.2020										

RQ ID	AT-T-10		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No		
Parent RQ	AT-T-09									
Title (Summary)	The Higher-Level Communication Middleware shall perform the semantic modelling of the data to be exchanged with MES and other higher-level management systems.									
Rationale (why, what, how)	Perform the semantic modelling of the data to be exchanged for interfacing Higher Level Communication Middleware with MES and other higher-level management systems.									
Reporter	ATLANTIS				Assignee			ATLANTIS, HOLONX		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No		
Pre-conditions	Semantic modelling of the data to be exchanged calls for use of appropriate ontology elements and semantic annotation of all exchanged data.									
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The exchanged data are described in terms of the kinds of entities that exist in the application environment, the classification and grouping of those entities and the structural interconnection among them.									
Exceptions	N/A									
Dependencies	AT-T-09									
Component/s	DSS, RSC, KBS, and other higher-level management systems e.g. ERP, MES, SCADA									
Date (change history)	23.11.2018; 10.09.2019; 10.04.2020									

General

RQ ID	AT-T-12		RQ Type		Non-Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, PRIMA, FILAR BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No		
Parent RQ	AT-NT-13									
Title (Summary)	The collected data shall be analyzed in order to evaluate the effectiveness, reliability, impact and acceptance of iQonic system.									
Rationale (why, what, how)	The analysis of the collected data will allow to extrapolate trends and assess the effective performance of iQonic, and to draw conclusions on the fulfillment of expected impact and stakeholder's expectations, both in terms of effectiveness / efficiency / reliability / objectives / expectations fulfilment analysis, as well as social and economic impact on the manufacturing environment.									
Reporter	ATLANTIS				Assignee			ATLANTIS, ALPES, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, FILAR		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No		
Pre-conditions	The evaluation of iQonic should be carried out based on methodology defined in T8.5.									
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The goal is to come up with a numerical "value proposition" for each future iQonic customers segment.									
Exceptions	N/A									
Dependencies	AT-NT-13									
Component/s	KBS, and other higher-level management systems e.g. ERP, MES, SCADA									
Date (change history)	23.11.2018; 10.09.2019; 10.04.2020									

RQ ID	AT-NT-13		RQ Type		Non-Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, PRIMA, FILAR BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No		
Parent RQ	N/A									
Title (Summary)	Data shall be collected and organized from pilot demonstrations.									
Rationale (why, what, how)	The data for technical, user acceptance and factory impact indicators shall be gathered in different formats (rtf documents for user acceptance, questionnaires / online instruments, spreadsheets with data for technical KPIs, data of ERP-MES-SCADA repositories and data from impact checklists), organized from pilot demonstrations.									
Reporter	ATLANTIS				Assignee			ATLANTIS, CORE, ALPES, PRIMA, FILAR, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No		
Pre-conditions	The data should be gathered according to the methodologies agreed within T8.4.									
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	N/A									
Exceptions	AT-T-12									
Dependencies	The data should be gathered according to the methodologies agreed within T8.4									
Component/s	KBS, and other higher-level management systems e.g. ERP, MES, SCADA									
Date (change history)	23.11.2018; 10.09.2019; 10.04.2020									

SENSAP

Inspection & metrology infrastructure to monitor the KPIs

RQ ID	SE-T-01		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No		
Parent RQ	N/A									
Title (Summary)	Visual Quality Inspection									
Rationale (why, what, how)	iQonic should define in all the use cases the requirements (e.g. resolution, accuracy, performance, classification of error types) and the potential positions in the production chain where the visual quality inspections will take place									
Reporter	SENSAP				Assignee			TAU, SENSAP, CORE		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No		
Pre-conditions	Well-defined defect categories by pilots (e.g., PRIMA Electro), a significant number of samples for analysis and evaluation of candidate inspection techniques									
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	As there is no standard for the acceptance criteria for the optoelectronics assembly than the criteria each of our Demo cases partners apply according to their quality standards, the acceptance criteria will be defined in each use case of our demo cases.									
Exceptions	N/A									
Dependencies	N/A									
Component/s	Daedalus, KBS, PdM, EvMod									
Date (change history)	11/01/2019, 03/01/2020, 28//4/2020									

RQ ID	SE-T-02		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	SE-T-01										
Title (Summary)	Visual Quality Inspection Methodologies and Techniques										
Rationale (why, what, how)	iQonic should investigate, update and develop the visual inspection system depicted from the user case requirements for the analysis of the quality of the final product or the semi-ready product throughout the production chain in order for a decision, based on the product quality, being made by the upper level systems of the iQonic platform.										
Reporter	SENSAP				Assignee			TAU, SENSAP, CORE, FORTH			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	Yes	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	Defect										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Image acquisition parameters (e.g. resolution, focal length) should be defined and known prior to any image pre-processing step. User requirement regarding product quality should be well defined.										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	SE-T-01,										
Component/s	Daedalus, KBS, PdM, EvMod										
Date (change history)	11/01/2019, 03/01/2020, 28//4/2020										

RQ ID	SE-T-03		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	SE-T-01										
Title (Summary)	In-Line metrology										
Rationale (why, what, how)	iQonic visual inspection system should be directly integrated into the production process. The product under inspection is measured without detours, ejections or separate test stations.										
Reporter	SENSAP				Assignee			TAU, SENSAP, CORE			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	A suitable position within production line should be defined.										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	A suitable acceptance criterion based on machine vision system installation will be the 99.7% of under specification image acquisition (Note: this is not exclusive).										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	SE-T-01, SE-T-02, HO-T-01,										
Component/s	Daedalus, KBS, PdM, EvMod										
Date (change history)	11/01/2019, 03/01/2020, 28//4/2020										

RQ ID	SE-T-21		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
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D2.5 Strategy implementation report

Status	<i>New</i>	Yes	<i>Agreed</i>	Yes	<i>Baselined</i>	No	<i>Rejected</i>	No
Parent RQ	SE-T-01							
Title (Summary)	In-Line metrology							
Rationale (why, what, how)	iQonic data acquisition system should pre-process generated images with suitable tools producing suitable images to be consumed by the high-level function of the iQonic system.							
Reporter	SENSAP			Assignee			SENSAP, CORE	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No
Pre-conditions	Machine vision systems already installed should support network communication protocols. Size of generated images should be adequate for data transmission.							
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	N/A							
Exceptions	N/A							
Dependencies	SE-T-01, SE-T-02, SE-T-03, HO-T-01							
Component/s	Daedalus, KBS, PdM, EvMod							
Date (change history)	03/01/2020, 28//4/2020							

Smart tagging for automatic setting-up the process chain parameters

RQ ID	SE-T-04		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No		
Parent RQ	N/A									
Title (Summary)	Smart Product									
Rationale (why, what, how)	A product should identify itself to the modules, providing all information required to accomplish its process on module. RFIDs/2D-Barcode are attached to the product following encoding standards (e.g. GS1-128), so that product-related information can be accessed									
Reporter	SENSAP				Assignee			TAU, SENSAP		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No		
Pre-conditions	Physical size of RFID/Tag									
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	N/A									
Exceptions	N/A									
Dependencies	SE-T-22									
Component/s	Daedalus, KBS									
Date (change history)	09/01/2019, 03/01/2020, 28//4/2020									

RQ ID	SE-T-05		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
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D2.5 Strategy implementation report

Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No
Parent RQ	SE-T-04							
Title (Summary)	Smart Tag Scanning							
Rationale (why, what, how)	A smart tagging scheme should be employed in order to linking all the data for each component to not only automate the loading process for programming the actuators, but also to minimize the possibility of using the wrong set-up of process parameters for any given product							
Reporter	SENSAP			Assignee			TAU, SENSAP	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No
Pre-conditions	Recipe data (set-up parameters) should be defined by each production phase employ this technology.							
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	N/A							
Exceptions	N/A							
Dependencies	SE-T-04, SE-T-22							
Component/s	Daedalus, KBS							
Date (change history)	09/01/2019; 03/01/2020; 28//4/2020							

RQ ID	SE-T-22	RQ Type		Technical	Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	Yes	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No
Parent RQ	SE-T-04							
Title (Summary)	Smart Tag database							
Rationale (why, what, how)	The set-up of process parameters for any given product (recipes) should be stored locally or in the cloud or if they are already contained at the end-user ERP/MES systems to be accessed and linked by the “smart” tagging system							
Reporter	SENSAP			Assignee			TAU, SENSAP, HOLONIX, ATLANTIS	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No
Pre-conditions	A local edge IoT device capable of storing recipe data locally, communication path established with the cloud solution. ERP/MES system endpoint interface (e.g. Rest API) providing recipe data.							
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	N/A							
Exceptions	N/A							
Dependencies	SE-T-04							
Component/s	Daedalus, KBS							
Date (change history)	03/03/2020; 28//4/2020							

Multisensorial data acquisition network for manufacturing opto-electrical parts

RQ ID	SE-T-06		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	N/A										
Title (Summary)	iQonic should be able to exchange data with existing infrastructure/assets (legacy systems) at the shop-floor										
Rationale (why, what, how)	A layer that facilitate the data exchange, flow and sharing between software components/services, based on industrial standards (e.g. OPC UA) should be designed and developed.										
Reporter	SENSAP				Assignee			SENSAP			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	Yes	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	Components diagrams along with its inputs/outputs definitions. Communication protocols support and data rates should be defined. Security of data transmission and integrity should be addressed.										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Security of data transmission and communication data rate should ensure a near “real-time” communication among s/w components.										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	N/A										
Component/s	Daedalus, KBS										
Date (change history)	02/01/2019; 03/03/2020: 30//4/2020										

RQ ID	SE-T-07		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	Yes	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	SE-T-06										
Title (Summary)	A common semantic data modelling.										
Rationale (why, what, how)	Modelling of the data to be exchanged by the acquisition module to the upper level sub-systems of the iQonic should be designed and agreed between involved partners.										
Reporter	SENSAP				Assignee			SENSAP, HOLONIX			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	User Requirements and use case analysis provides all the needed data from the ShopFloor the acquisition system will collect. All the data sources should be available.										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	N/A										
Exceptions	In case there is no suitable data source, additional sensors should be installed.										
Dependencies	SE-T-06,										
Component/s	Daedalus, iLike Machines, KBS										
Date (change history)	02/01/2019; 03/03/2020; 30//4/2020										

RQ ID	SE-T-08		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	N/A										
Title (Summary)	Access to physical data using sensors										
Rationale (why, what, how)	The iQonic will provide the necessary mechanisms for sensing (i.e. to extract information from heterogenous data sources both physical and software assets)										
Reporter	SENSAP				Assignee			SENSAP			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	Data sources defined. Properly defined position and type of sensor. Communication access to the software data sources using standard protocols.										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	N/A										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	SE-T-06, SE-T-07,										
Component/s	Daedalus, iLike Machines, KBS										
Date (change history)	02/01/2019; 03/03/2020; 30//4/2020										

RQ ID	SE-T-09		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	N/A										
Title (Summary)	The traceability of data collected, and machine/industrial assets observations should be guaranteed.										
Rationale (why, what, how)	All the data collected and extracted from machines/industrial assets must be related to a standard reference system to enable the connection, mapping and tracking of the extracted data and observations to machines/industrial assets, data analytics services, etc.										
Reporter	SENSAP				Assignee			SENSAP, HOLONIX, ATLANTIS			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	N/A										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	N/A										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	CO-T-01, CO-T-02										
Component/s	Daedalus, iLike Machines, KBS										
Date (change history)	02/01/2019; 03/03/2020; 30//4/2020										

Integration of software – hardware platforms and tools

RQ ID	SE-T-10		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	N/A										
Title (Summary)	iQonic needs to operate in a network-based environment										
Rationale (why, what, how)	To use web-based technologies to allow all the components and layers within the system to connect with other part of the system itself that is available in the same network										
Reporter	SENSAP				Assignee			FRAUNHOFER			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	N/A										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	N/A										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	N/A										
Component/s	ALL										
Date (change history)	02/01/2019; 03/03/2020; 30//4/2020										

RQ ID	SE-T-11		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	N/A										
Title (Summary)	The system should leverage standard as much as possible										
Rationale (why, what, how)	To design and develop a layer that deeply relies on standards to support and facilitate the integration of legacy and heterogeneous machines/industrial assets										
Reporter	SENSAP				Assignee			FRAUNHOFER, SENSAP, TAU			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	Yes	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	N/A										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	N/A										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	N/A										
Component/s	Daedalus, iLike Machine										
Date (change history)	02/01/2019; 03/03/2020; 30//4/2020										

RQ ID	SE-T-12		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	N/A										
Title (Summary)	To design, develop and install a "non" intrusive system										
Rationale (why, what, how)	The system should not use communication technologies that interfere with existing communication infrastructure										
Reporter	SENSAP				Assignee			FRAUNHOFER, SENSAP, TAU			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	N/A										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	N/A										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	SE-T-10, SE-T-11,										
Component/s	ALL										
Date (change history)	02/01/2019; 03/03/2020; 30//4/2020										

RQ ID	SE-T-13		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	Yes	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	N/A										
Title (Summary)	iQonic platform and communications should be secure										
Rationale (why, what, how)	Several data sources generate data that needs to be collected and sent over public and/or private networks to a possibly remote infrastructure in order to be analyzed. In the same way, data generated on a remote location received back to the iQonic module in order to integrate the received information into the process										
Reporter	SENSAP				Assignee			FRAUNHOFER, SENSAP, HOLONIX			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	Yes	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	Secure mechanism should be supported throughout all the data flow of iQonic system										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	N/A										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	SE-NT-19,										
Component/s	Daedalus, iLike Machine										
Date (change history)	02/01/2019; 03/03/2020; 30//4/2020										

RQ ID	SE-T-14		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	N/A										
Title (Summary)	iQonic system should employ modularity principle.										
Rationale (why, what, how)	System components should be loosely coupled and reconfigurable on a plug and play principle so as the system be able to respond to changing customer requirements and overcome internal system failures.										
Reporter	SENSAP				Assignee			FRAUNHOFER			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	Yes	<i>Medium</i>	Yes	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	N/A										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	N/A										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	N/A										
Component/s	ALL										
Date (change history)	09/01/2019; 03/03/2020; 30//4/2020										

RQ ID	SE-NT-15		RQ Type		Non-technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	N/A										
Title (Summary)	iQonic platform architecture shall support cloud infrastructure										
Rationale (why, what, how)	A cloud infrastructure should be supported so as the iQonic could aligned with Industry 4.0 specification and benefit from it (secure, scalability, etc)										
Reporter	SENSAP				Assignee			FRAUNHOFER, HOLONIX			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	Yes	<i>Medium</i>	Yes	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	N/A										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	N/A										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	N/A										
Component/s	ALL										
Date (change history)	02/01/2019; 03/03/2020; 30//4/2020										

RQ ID	SE-NT-16		RQ Type	Non-technical		Use Cases	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No
Parent RQ	N/A							
Title (Summary)	iQonic platform							
Rationale (why, what, how)	The iQonic platform shall provide technical support, business support services to platform users.							
Reporter	SENSAP			Assignee			FRAUNHOFER	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	Yes	<i>Optional</i>	No
Pre-conditions	A single point for providing services							
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	N/A							
Exceptions	N/A							
Dependencies	N/A							
Component/s	ALL							
Date (change history)	11/01/2019; 03/03/2020; 30//4/2020							

RQ ID	SE-NT-17		RQ Type	Non-technical		Use Cases	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No
Parent RQ	N/A							
Title (Summary)	iQonic platform							
Rationale (why, what, how)	Architecture shall comply with the emerging standards (RAMI 4.0 and the Industrial Internet Consortium)							
Reporter	SENSAP			Assignee			FRAUNHOFER	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	Yes	<i>Optional</i>	No
Pre-conditions	N/A							
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	N/A							
Exceptions	N/A							
Dependencies	N/A							
Component/s	CO-T-04							
Date (change history)	11/01/2019; 03/03/2020; 30//4/2020							

RQ ID	SE-NT-18		RQ Type		Non-technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No		
Parent RQ	N/A									
Title (Summary)	iQonic Data modelling									
Rationale (why, what, how)	The semantics of modelling in iQonic must be based on standardized meta-models and ontologies and should support the production and be extensible.									
Reporter	SENSAP				Assignee			FRAUNHOFER. ATLANTIS, HOLONIX		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	Yes	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No		
Pre-conditions	N/A									
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	N/A									
Exceptions	N/A									
Dependencies	N/A									
Component/s	KBS									
Date (change history)	11/01/2019; 03/03/2020; 30//4/2020									

RQ ID	SE-NT-19		RQ Type		Non-technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No		
Parent RQ	N/A									
Title (Summary)	iQonic Security									
Rationale (why, what, how)	The security framework shall ensure confidentiality of data and prevent unauthorized access to the platform.									
Reporter	SENSAP				Assignee			FRAUNHOFER, HOLONIX		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	Yes	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No		
Pre-conditions	N/A									
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	N/A									
Exceptions	N/A									
Dependencies	SE-T-11, SE-T-13, SE-NT-17, PO-T-12									
Component/s	iLike Machines									
Date (change history)	11/01/2019; 03/03/2020; 30//4/2020									

RQ ID	SE-T-20		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Provide a set of Human Machine Interfaces (HMI) to allow humans to interact with it								
Rationale (why, what, how)	iQonic should provide graphical interfaces for data visualization The data visualization will ensure the visualization of the KPI over the time, the possibility to define new KPIs and the necessary mechanisms to support the human in the decision making process.								
Reporter	SENSAP				Assignee			FRAUNHOFER, POLIMI	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	Yes	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	KPIs defined and calculated. Data visualization type and method defined.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	N/A								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	PO-T-13								
Component/s	Daedalus, i-Like Machines, PdM, CPS, DSS, EvMod								
Date (change history)	02/01/2019; 03/03/2020; 30/4/2020								

FICONTEC

The RQs FIC-T-11 was deleted as this was exactly the same as FIC-T-10.

Hardware for automated assembly

RQ ID	FIC-T-01		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, HiLase
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Assembly process chain								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The assembly process chains used at the end users should be documented to allow FICONTEC to make a conceptual study about possible assembly machine layout for the project.								
Reporter	FICONTEC				Assignee			ALPES, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	Yes	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Assembly process finally developed and established at end users								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	A document is established and proven by the end users listing the exact assembly process flow including all components used, allowing FIC to develop the automated assembly process for its machines.								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	FIC-T-01, FIC-T-02, FIC-T-03, FIC-T-04								
Component/s	N/A								
Date (change history)	16.01.2019; 18/02/2020; 12/05/2020								

RQ ID	FIC-T-02	RQ Type	Technical			Use Cases	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, HiLase		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	FIC-T-01								
Title (Summary)	Component size and quantity								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The size of the photonic components to be handled and assembled should be documented to choose a proper handling mechanism.								
Reporter	FICONTEC			Assignee			ALPES, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Components are known by the end users								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Document listing the component size and quantity exists and is shared with the project partners.								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	Individual components from PRIMA Electro, ALPES and Brightherwave which need to be assembled								
Component/s	Assembly machines for each end user								
Date (change history)	16.01.2019; 18/02/2020; 12/05/2020								

RQ ID	FIC-T-03	RQ Type	Technical			Use Cases	ALPES, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, HiLase		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	FIC-T-01								
Title (Summary)	Alignment processes								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The concepts used for the alignment of optical components needs to be documented. This could be either passive (vision based) or active (device under operation) processes. The alignment tolerances should be reported to decide for a proper machine layout.								
Reporter	FICONTEC			Assignee			ALPES, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Alignment process flow established at customer side								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The alignment process flow is documented in a written way including all required process details and required accuracies.								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	Individual alignment process flows from PRIMA Electro, ALPES and Brightherwave which are used during the assembly of their products								
Component/s	Assembly machines for each end user								
Date (change history)	16.01.2019; 18/02/2020; 12/05/2020								

RQ ID	FIC-T-04	RQ Type			Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, HiLase
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	FIC-T-01								
Title (Summary)	Fixation processes								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The way how the optical components are fixed after alignment needs to be documented to allow for a proper machine layout. This includes the used material for fixation for bonding or epoxy-based processes.								
Reporter	FICONTEC				Assignee			ALPES, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Components, modules and assembly process flow defined								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Document listing the fixation process including for epoxy-based processes: epoxy type, wavelength and time and for soldering processes: type of solder, temperature, solder profile, soldering time								
Exceptions	Not valid in case no fixation is included in the assembly process flow								
Dependencies	FIC-T-01, FIC-T-02, FIC-T-02, FIC-T-03								
Component/s	Individual components which need to be assembled								
Date (change history)	16.01.2019; 18/02/2020; 12/05/2020								

RQ ID	FIC-T-05	RQ Type			Technical		Use Cases		FORTH
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Inspection system								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The characteristics of the digital adaptive optics system need to be known for implementation into the machine.								
Reporter	FICONTEC				Assignee			FORTH	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Components from end users								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The inspection system is included in one of the assembly machines from ficonTEC for inspection of components of one of the use cases								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	FIC-T-06; FIC-T-07								
Component/s	Components from end users								
Date (change history)	16.01.2019; 18/02/2020; 12/05/2020								

RQ ID	FIC-T-06		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		FORTH		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	FIC-T-05										
Title (Summary)	Hardware of inspection system										
Rationale (why, what, how)	The dimensions and weight as well as typical hardware interface like electrical and mechanical connections of the digital adaptive optics system needs to be known for implementation into the machine.										
Reporter	FICONTEC				Assignee			FORTH			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	Inspection system is finally developed and proven with parts of end users at FORTH										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Hardware of inspection system is known as bill of material as well as 3D drawing										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	N/A										
Component/s	Hardware components of inspection system										
Date (change history)	16.01.2019; 18/02/2020; 12/05/2020										

RQ ID	FIC-T-07		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		FORTH		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	FIC-T-05										
Title (Summary)	Software interface of inspection system										
Rationale (why, what, how)	The software interface of the digital adaptive optics system needs to be known for implementation into the machine.										
Reporter	FICONTEC				Assignee			FORTH			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	Software of inspection system is finally developed and proven with parts of end users at FORTH										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Software of inspection system is integrated into FIC machines and can be used with components from end users.										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	N/A										
Component/s	Algorithms of software inspection system										
Date (change history)	16.01.2019; 18/02/2020; 12/05/2020										

RQ ID	FIC-T-08	RQ Type			Technical	Use Cases		ALPES, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, HiLase	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Sensor data								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The amount of required sensor data and the format in which the data needs to be saved needs to be known to allow for use of evaluation of this data for artificial intelligence algorithms.								
Reporter	FICONTEC				Assignee		FORTH		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Sensors are installed and implemented into the assembly machine								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Sensor data is saved in a data file allowing a further use by the project partners								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	N/A								
Component/s	UDP stream and machine database								
Date (change history)	16.01.2019; 18/02/2020; 12/05/2020								

RQ ID	FIC-T-09	RQ Type			Technical	Use Cases		ALPES, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, HiLase	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Electronic nose								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The interface to the electronic nose needs to be known for proper implementation into the assembly machine.								
Reporter	FICONTEC				Assignee		SACMI		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Electronic nose developed and interfaces established								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Interfaces of electronic nose are defined and documented								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	N/A								
Component/s	Hardware and electric connections of electronic nose								
Date (change history)	16.01.2019; 18/02/2020; 12/05/2020								

RQ ID	FIC-T-10		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, HiLase
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Electronic nose								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The chemicals which can be detected by the electronic noise should be known to plan for a proper use in the assembly machine								
Reporter	FICONTEC				Assignee			SACMI	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Material to be detected by electronic nose must be known								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Electronic nose can detect the required materials within the environment of an assembly machine								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	N/A								
Component/s	Epoxy which need to be detected, further materials of interest								
Date (change history)	16.01.2019; 18/02/2020; 12/05/2020								

SACMI

Environmental operational condition

RQ ID	SA-T-02		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Environment experimental condition (temperature and humidity) shall be examined within the sampling chamber.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The sampling chamber and the sample itself shall be involved within the sub-system and components. and it shall be checked that the range of temperature and humidity within the chamber are, respectively, between 0° and 60 °C, and between 0% and 60 %. The scope is to inform the operators of the assignee on the procedure to follow and the parameters to respect in order to avoid mistakes leading to the malfunction of the electronic nose.								
Reporter	SACMI				Assignee			ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	Yes	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	The electronic nose is installed correctly								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Temperature and humidity of the sample are within the correct range								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	N/A								
Component/s	Defect detection system								
Date (change history)	10.12.2018; 03.03.2020; 29.04.2020								

RQ ID	SA-T-03		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No		
Parent RQ	N/A									
Title (Summary)	Environmental operational condition shall be examined within the room where the electronic nose is placed.									
Rationale (why, what, how)	The room where the electronic nose is placed shall be part of the involved sub-system and components and shall respect some conditions, i.e. it has a temperature range from 15 to 30 °C, relative humidity range from 0 to 50 %, in absence of dust in the air. The scope is to inform the assignee's operators on the environment characteristics and parameters to be respected since he is not informed on the parameters and procedures to respect.									
Reporter	SACMI				Assignee			ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	Yes	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No		
Pre-conditions	The electronic nose is installed correctly									
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Temperature and humidity of the environment are within the correct range									
Exceptions	N/A									
Dependencies	N/A									
Component/s	Defect detection system									
Date (change history)	10.12.2018; 03.03.2020; 29.04.2020									

Sensor array

RQ ID	SA-C-05		RQ Type		Constraint		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No		
Parent RQ	N/A									
Title (Summary)	The operator or control system shall wait for stationary signal from the electronic nose.									
Rationale (why, what, how)	The scope of this constraint is to inform the users on timing for the sampling. If the sampling time is not long enough to achieve a stationary signal, the output could not be representative of the sample. Approximately 5-10 minutes are required before starting sampling since the gas sample is presented to the electronic nose, or a change in measurement conditions occurs. As a consequence, the sampling rate of the device is not higher than one sample (or one batch of samples) every 5 minutes. Incorrect measurements can be generated if the operator does not wait the requested time because he/she is not informed, or the process of the user does not allow to wait 5 to 10 minutes.									
Reporter	SACMI				Assignee			FRAUNHOFER, ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No		
Pre-conditions	The electronic nose is installed correctly and is measuring									
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Sensor signals are stable									
Exceptions	N/A									
Dependencies	SA-T-02; SA-T-03; SA-T-07; SA-T-08; SA-T-09									
Component/s	Defect detection system									
Date (change history)	10.12.2018; 03.03.2020; 29.04.2020									

RQ ID	SA-C-06		RQ Type		Constraint		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	Yes	<i>Baselined</i>	No	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	SA-C-05								
Title (Summary)	Maximum number of different sensing signals to be recognized by the sensor array chosen to measure the concentration of particles in the air								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The scope of this requirement is to inform the assignee of this constraint that the classification algorithm is less efficient when the instrument is trained to detect more than 4 similar odors. If the instrument is trained to recognize a high number of odors with similar chemical composition, the probability of having wrong classifications increases.								
Reporter	SACMI				Assignee			ALL	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	The odors under study in each use case have been defined								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The number of odors under study for each use case is less than 5								
Exceptions	If the odors correspond to substances with very different chemical composition, the number can be increased.								
Dependencies	N/A								
Component/s	Defect detection system, use-case production process.								
Date (change history)	10.12.2018; 03.03.2020; 29.04.2020								

Electronic nose

RQ ID	SA-T-07		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Optimal and maximum tube length for connecting the electronic nose to the sampling chamber.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The scope is to inform the assignee on the maximum distance between the electronic nose and the chamber. If they are more than 2mt distant the electronic nose cannot sample the odor. Main failure causes (why): The operator is not informed on the parameters to be respected.								
Reporter	SACMI				Assignee			FRAUNHOFER, ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	Yes	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	The layout of the defect detection system has been defined								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Tube length less than 2mt								
Exceptions	If more distance is required, it is possible to use an additional pump to increase gas flow.								
Dependencies	N/A								
Component/s	Defect detection system								
Date (change history)	10.12.2018; 03.03.2020; 29.04.2020								

RQ ID	SA-T-08		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	The electronic nose shall be powered using an external stable power supply								
Rationale (why, what, how)	An external stable power supply (220V, 50 Hz, max power consumption required 200W) shall be involved within the sub-system and components. The operator shall be informed on the parameters to be respected (220 V 50 Hz) since wrong values of the voltage or the current can damage the device.								
Reporter	SACMI				Assignee		FRAUNHOFER, ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	Yes	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	The layout of the defect detection system has been defined								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The electronic nose is powered								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	N/A								
Component/s	Defect detection system								
Date (change history)	10.12.2018; 03.03.2020; 29.04.2020								

RQ ID	SA-T-09		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	The device shall be placed on a flat surface; its size is 40x20x50 cm and it weighs 15-20 Kg.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The scope of this requirement is to make awareness of the space required for the instrumentation, which include the electronic nose itself, the sampling chamber and a tube connecting the chamber and the instrument. If the room for the sensor is not adequate or the operator is not informed on the parameters and procedures to be respected the instrument will not work properly.								
Reporter	SACMI				Assignee		FRAUNHOFER, ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	Yes	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	The layout of the defect detection system has been defined								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The electronic nose is in a stable position								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	N/A								
Component/s	Defect detection system								
Date (change history)	10.12.2018; 03.03.2020; 29.04.2020								

FRAUNHOFER

Design and architecture of process chain and strategies

RQ ID	F-IOF-T-01	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	The process chain and strategy for all KPF and solution functionalities.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	Process chain architectures and strategies for photonics system assembly have to be transferred from standard, linear and sequential designs to a mixed architecture that contains feedback loops and interfaces to software intelligence. In particular emerging developments from Artificial Intelligence about planning and adapting multi-variable processes shall be taken into account, respective interfaces to hardware process-based functionalities have to be determined and qualitatively parametrized.								
Reporter	FRAUNHOFER			Assignee			FRAUNHOFER, FICONTEC, TAU		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Available iQonic hardware and software architecture.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Feedback-loop descriptions for manufacturing processes of the use cases.								
Exceptions	Feedback-loop might not be reasonable nor available for small quantity use cases.								
Dependencies	n.a.								
Component/s	All hardware and software components of the iQonic architecture.								
Date (change history)	13.01.2019; 29.02.2020; 02.05.2020								

RQ ID	F-IOF-T-02	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	The process chain and strategy for all KPF and solution functionalities.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	Process chain architecture and strategies for photonics system assembly shall contain different layers representing different levels of details. The first, generalized and qualitative layer shall be composed of main process hardware/ software building blocks and interfaces, the second layer shall be quantitative in terms building block descriptions and main requirements, the third layer shall contain detailed quantitative requirements for building blocks and its sub-building blocks, and interfaces.								
Reporter	FRAUNHOFER			Assignee			FRAUNHOFER, FICONTEC, TAU		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Available iQonic hardware and software architecture.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Level of detailing from process building blocks down to quantitative process parameters available.								
Exceptions	Feedback-loop quantitative process parameters might not be reasonable nor available for small quantity use cases.								
Dependencies	F-IOF-T-01								
Component/s	All hardware and software components of the iQonic architecture.								
Date (change history)	13.01.2019; 29.02.2020; 02.05.2020								

Process Chain

RQ ID	F-IOF-T-03	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Process chain building blocks and interfaces description								
Rationale (why, what, how)	A common descriptor for process chain building block (or “architecture component”) properties and performances, either hardware or software based, shall allow for a unified solution functionality description as well as for a unified hardware and software interface description.								
Reporter	FRAUNHOFER			Assignee			FRAUNHOFER		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Available iQonic hardware and software architecture.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	n.a.								
Exceptions	n.a.								
Dependencies	F-IOF-T-01, F-IOF-T-02								
Component/s	All hardware and software components of the iQonic architecture.								
Date (change history)	13.01.2019; 29.02.2020; 02.05.2020								

RQ ID	F-IOF-T-04	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	F-IOF-T-03								
Title (Summary)	Process chain hardware building blocks and interfaces description								
Rationale (why, what, how)	A common descriptor for process chain hardware building block (or “architecture component”) properties and performances, shall allow for a unified solution functionality description as well as for a unified hardware interface description. The hardware descriptor shall focus on procedural, optical, mechanical, electrical, thermal, environmental, and assembly economics issues of the assembly chain.								
Reporter	FRAUNHOFER			Assignee			FRAUNHOFER		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Available iQonic hardware and software architecture.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	One descriptor per hardware process chain (preparation, feeding, handling, alignment, bonding).								
Exceptions	n.a.								
Dependencies	F-IOF-T-01, F-IOF-T-02, F-IOF-T-03								
Component/s	All hardware components of the iQonic architecture.								
Date (change history)	13.01.2019; 29.02.2020; 02.05.2020								

RQ ID	F-IOF-T-05		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	F-IOF-T-03								
Title (Summary)	Process chain software building blocks and interfaces description								
Rationale (why, what, how)	A common descriptor for process chain software building block (or “architecture component”) properties and performances, shall allow for a unified solution functionality description as well as for a unified software interface description. The software descriptor shall focus on procedural and multi-parameter control, usability and inter-operability amongst different photonics assembly platforms.								
Reporter	FRAUNHOFER				Assignee			FRAUNHOFER	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Available iQonic hardware and software architecture.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	One descriptor per software process chain.								
Exceptions	n.a.								
Dependencies	F-IOF-T-01, F-IOF-T-02, F-IOF-T-03								
Component/s	All hardware components of the iQonic architecture.								
Date (change history)	13.01.2019; 29.02.2020; 02.05.2020								

Solution Validation

RQ ID	F-IOF-T-06		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Solution validation based on functional parameters								
Rationale (why, what, how)	Individual solutions for the iQonic process chain shall be characterized by a matrix of KPF, independent from their application to individual use cases. Functionality test cases have to be defined that allow for simple, statistically reliable testing. In case functionality cannot be tested stand-alone, standardized interfaces to the process environment and control have to be defined, e.g. by defining hardware and/ or software simulators.								
Reporter	FRAUNHOFER				Assignee			FRAUNHOFER	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Available iQonic hardware and software architecture, processed use cases.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Use case related KPI, see D2.4.								
Exceptions	No KPI measurements eventually reasonable for low quantity use cases.								
Dependencies	F-IOF-T-01, F-IOF-T-02, F-IOF-T-03, F-IOF-T-04, F-IOF-T-05								
Component/s	All hardware and software components of the iQonic architecture.								
Date (change history)	13.01.2019; 29.02.2020; 02.05.2020								

D2.5 Strategy implementation report

RQ ID	F-IOF-T-07	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		generic	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	F-IOF-T-06								
Title (Summary)	Hardware process based solution validation based on functional parameters								
Rationale (why, what, how)	Hardware based process solution validation shall be defined in a way that statistically reliable testing can be done for a relevant number of processed samples. Procedures to evaluate the samples have to be defined. The samples shall reflect, if suitable, main features of user cases, but shall be independent for easier processing of in particular high numbers of samples for statistical reasons. If needed, a software simulator shall be used for the defined variation of software inputs.								
Reporter	FRAUNHOFER			Assignee			FRAUNHOFER		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Available iQonic hardware architecture, processed use cases.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Use case, hardware process related KPI, see D2.4.								
Exceptions	No KPI measurements eventually reasonable for low quantity use cases.								
Dependencies	F-IOF-T-01, F-IOF-T-02, F-IOF-T-03, F-IOF-T-04, F-IOF-T-06								
Component/s	All hardware components of the iQonic architecture.								
Date (change history)	13.01.2019; 29.02.2020; 02.05.2020								

RQ ID	F-IOF-T-08	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		generic	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	F-IOF-T-06								
Title (Summary)	Software process based solution validation based on functional parameters								
Rationale (why, what, how)	For software based process solution validation a procedure following the guidelines of ISO/IEC/IEEE 29119 Software Testing standards shall be applied. Of particular interest is testing vs. a variability of hardware process parameter inputs, e.g. for range limits or out of bounds values, to prove stability of the software based process solution. If needed, a hardware simulator shall be used for the variation of these inputs.								
Reporter	FRAUNHOFER			Assignee			FRAUNHOFER		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Available iQonic software architecture, processed use cases.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Use case, software process related KPI, see D2.4.								
Exceptions	No KPI measurements eventually reasonable for low quantity use cases.								
Dependencies	F-IOF-T-01, F-IOF-T-02, F-IOF-T-03, F-IOF-T-05, F-IOF-T-06								
Component/s	All software components of the iQonic architecture.								
Date (change history)	13.01.2019; 29.02.2020; 02.05.2020								

Use Case Demonstration Evaluation

RQ ID	F-IOF-T-09		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Evaluation performance methodology and requirements matrix								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The evaluation methodology shall be deterministic, addressing a matrix of KPF requirements for each use case. In the same time, the methodology shall be adapted to the individual use cases and their specific requirements. In particular, evaluation procedures and their boundary conditions, e.g. number of samples to be processed for reliable statistics, test procedures on the samples to prove their performance etc., shall be defined to allow planning for the use case providers. The methodology shall also provide information about the progress vs. state of the art.								
Reporter	FRAUNHOFER				Assignee			FRAUNHOFER	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Available iQonic software architecture, processed and evaluated use cases.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Common and use case related KPI, see D2.4.								
Exceptions	No KPI evaluation eventually reasonable for low quantity use cases.								
Dependencies	F-IOF-T-06, F-IOF-T-07, F-IOF-T-08								
Component/s	All hardware and software components of the iQonic architecture.								
Date (change history)	13.01.2019; 29.02.2020; 02.05.2020								

BRUNEL

Production Logic

RQ ID	BU-T-01		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases #		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, FiconTEC (All Manufacturers and OEMS)
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Full production process (Process Flow Chart), Precedence Chart, Station and Total production Cycle Times								
Rationale (why, what, how)	A full understanding of the production process described by OEM and the Manufacturer (each with their own interpretation and manufacturers with their interferences)								
Reporter	FRAUNHOFER				Assignee			All Manufacturers and OEM	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Introduction and explanation of each subprocess by appropriate experts								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Each team member be fully aware of the implementation of the whole production process								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	N/A								
Component/s	SAC, FAC, Mirror, Lenz								
Date (change history)	28.12.2018; 25.10.2019; 25.02.2020								

RQ ID	BU-T-02	RQ Type	Technical		Use Cases #	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, FiconTEC (All Manufacturers and OEMS)		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No
Parent RQ	N/A							
Title (Summary)	Full Description/Specification/Tolerances/Equipment/ of Production Processes							
Rationale (why, what, how)	A full understanding of the production process described by OEM and the Manufacturer (each with their own interpretation and manufacturers with their interferences). All necessary steps with clear indicators and measurements, tolerances, and all necessary technical details of processing that impact quality and material flow.							
Reporter	FRAUNHOFER			Assignee		All Manufacturers and OEM		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No
Pre-conditions	Consistency in languages and terminologies							
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Understanding of the each production subprocess and the associate function in the whole manufacture							
Exceptions	N/A							
Dependencies	BU-T-01							
Component/s	SAC, FAC, Mirror, Lenz							
Date (change history)	28.12.2018; 25.02.2019; 25.02.2020							

Existing Machine State and Control Logic

RQ ID	BU-T-03	RQ Type	Technical		Use Cases #	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, FiconTEC (All Manufacturers and OEMS), Shadow		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No
Parent RQ	N/A							
Title (Summary)	Process Control Architecture, Mechanisms, Logic, Process Capability, Sensors and Actuation							
Rationale (why, what, how)	A full understanding of the production process control logic sensing and actuation. What if scenarios? Monitoring and Actuation Capabilities, flexibilities and constraints. This information linked to the quality evaluation and process capability will lead to identification of innovation steps for dexterity and flexibility in the production process (Shadow Robot). Result: Identification of Gap in technology							
Reporter	FRAUNHOFER			Assignee		All Manufacturers and OEM and Shadow Robot		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No
Pre-conditions	Understanding will combine data analytics and expert knowledge from heterogeneous sources of monitoring, processing, evaluation and identification							
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The identification should consider availability of both data and expert factors and reflect their impacts on dexterity and flexibility							
Exceptions	N/A							
Dependencies	BU-T-01, BU-T-02							
Component/s	Knowledge Base System, Shadow Robot							
Date (change history)	28.12.2018; 25.02.2019;25.02.2020							

Product and Process Quality Monitoring

RQ ID	BU-T-04	RQ Type	Technical			Use Cases #	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, FiconTEC (All Manufacturers and OEMS), Shadow		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Quality Control and Management								
Rationale (why, what, how)	Quality control techniques, on-line and off-line, reporting mechanism, corrective actions, feedback time, actions and reactions, tolerances, machine state and product quality links (if exists).								
Reporter	BRUNEL			Assignee			All Manufacturers and OEM and Shadow Robot		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Integration of the monitoring, prediction and identification results to quality control								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The control loop will feedback quality according to each pre-selected setting having the overall performance indicator and presents the optimal remedy action should be taken to improve product quality								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	BU-T-01, BU-T-02, BU-T-03								
Component/s	SAC, FAC, Mirror, Lenz, Knowledge Base System, Shadow Robot								
Date (change history)	28.12.2018; 25.02.2019; 25.06.2020								

RQ ID	BU-T-05	RQ Type	Technical			Use Cases #	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, FiconTEC (All Manufacturers and OEMS), Shadow Robot		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Machine State and Product/Process Quality Mapping								
Rationale (why, what, how)	Detailed event analytics of the machine state and its relation with production quality. Real-time data acquisition capabilities, off-line quality assessments, expert views on types of defect and causal relations.								
Reporter	BRUNEL			Assignee			All Manufacturers and OEM and Shadow Robot		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	The Knowledge Base System (KBS) shall store the whole information related to production processes, assets and products								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Event-based model provides faster and better clustering and classification while relating inputs, outputs and KPIs								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	BU-T-02, BU-T-04								
Component/s	SAC, FAC, Mirror, Lenz, Knowledge Base System								
Date (change history)	28.12.2018; 25.02.2019; 25.08.2019								

RQ ID	BU-T-06		RQ Type	Technical		Use Cases #	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, FiconTEC (All Manufacturers and OEMS)		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	BU-T-05								
Title (Summary)	Machine Maintenance and failure modes								
Rationale (why, what, how)	Reports and FMEA on machine tools failure, impact, risk and potential relationship between MTBF and quality assurance.								
Reporter	BRUNEL				Assignee	All Manufacturers and OEM and Shadow Robot			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Event model will combine product machine Maintenance and failure modes from heterogeneous sources of monitoring-diagnosis-prediction-detection.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The event model should provide maintenance and failures indicators such as events, faults, alarms and warning from shop-floor.								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	BU-T-02, BU-T-04, BU-T-05								
Component/s	SAC, FAC, Mirror, Lenz, Knowledge Base System								
Date (change history)	28.12.2018; 25.02.2019; 25.10.2020								

Flexible, Predictive Manufacturing Platform

RQ ID	BU-T-07		RQ Type	Technical		Use Cases #	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, FiconTEC (All Manufacturers and OEMS)		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Agile, Dexterous and Responsive Production System								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The new robotics, sensing and actuation technologies to be deployed for online predictive control system								
Reporter	BRUNEL				Assignee	All Manufacturers and OEM and Shadow Robot			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	The embed event-based algorithm should provide accurate and precise prediction and control commands for reliable manufacture								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The deployed new robotics, sensing and actuation technologies supplies reliable and safe online prediction and control								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	BU-T-02, BU-T-04, BU-T-05, BU-T-06								
Component/s	SAC, FAC, Mirror, Lenz, Knowledge Base System, Shadow Robot								
Date (change history)	28.12.2018; 25.02.2019; 25.10.2020								

Circular Economy Modelling

RQ ID	BU-T-09	RQ Type	Technical			Use Cases #	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, FiconTEC (All Manufacturers and OEMS)		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Principles of Circular Economy embedded in Manufacturing Control and Planning								
Rationale (why, what, how)	Understanding of the material evolution throughout production process, post production and reusability/recyclability								
Reporter	BRUNEL			Assignee			All Manufacturers and OEM and Shadow Robot		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Understandings of the whole production process and the evolution of the product material								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Recommendations and suggestions should be provided that quantify the underlying recycling percentage of the materials after possible occurrence of product defects								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	BU-T-04, BU-T-06, BU-T-07								
Component/s	SAC, FAC, Mirror, Lenz, Knowledge Base System, Shadow Robot								
Date (change history)	28.12.2018; 25.02.2019; 25.10.2020								

RQ ID	BU-T-10	RQ Type	Technical			Use Cases #	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, other partners involved in Reverse logistics and DSS (e.g. Atlantis)		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Production Economics, Environmental Impact Analysis, Logistics and Reverse Logistics								
Rationale (why, what, how)	Full EIA of the production system and end products, production, recycling and reusability economic and sustainability analysis. Understanding the practical and technological barriers and suggestions for overcoming them.								
Reporter	BRUNEL			Assignee			All Manufacturers and OEM and Shadow Robot		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	A full understanding of the whole production process, the evolution of the material, the recycling percentage of the material, and the relationships among the material consumption, product quality and environment impact								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Recommendations and guidance rules should be given for an acceptable/optimal balance among production efficiency, environmental impact, product quality and other KPIs								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	BU-T-03, BU-T-04, BU-T-05, BU-T-06, BU-T-07, BU-T-08								
Component/s	SAC, FAC, Mirror, Lenz, Knowledge Base System, Shadow Robot								
Date (change history)	28.12.2018; 25.02.2019; 25.10.2020								

CORE

Early Malfunctional detection and prediction interface engine

RQ ID	CO-T-01	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	The machine learning algorithms must have access to synchronized data (common timestamp).								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The common timestamp will ensure that the data from the sensors and machines can be properly matched with each other to identify anomalies.								
Reporter	CORE			Assignee			HOLONIX, ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, SENSAP		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	N/A								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Having a Unix timestamp								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	N/A								
Component/s	Inference Engine								
Date (change history)	21.12.2018; 03.03.2020; 29.04.2020								

RQ ID	CO-T-02	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	CO-T-01								
Title (Summary)	Definitions of Normal Operation state and Anomaly state.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The data must be provided with labels that explicitly describe the state of the machine at every timestamp or at least when it operated with erroneous conditions (can be time range instead of singular timestamps – start/end).								
Reporter	CORE			Assignee			HOLONIX, ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	N/A								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Single encoding of observed anomalies								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	N/A								
Component/s	Inference Engine								
Date (change history)	21.12.2018; 03.03.2020; 29.04.2020								

RQ ID	CO-T-03		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	CO-T-02								
Title (Summary)	Definitions of the types of the errors in the Anomaly state.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The data must be provided with labels that explicitly describe the type of error (alarm codes, quality of the products, type of malfunction, etc.) when in Anomaly state, or suitable metadata formats (fused expert knowledge).								
Reporter	CORE				Assignee			HOLONIX, ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	N/A								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Encoding of known state, Performance metrics of the process								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	N/A								
Component/s	Inference Engine								
Date (change history)	21.12.2018; 03.03.2020; 29.04.2020								

RQ ID	CO-T-04		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Specifications of communication protocols.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	This will allow to adapt the inference modules integration to every use case scenario.								
Reporter	CORE				Assignee			HOLONIX, ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, SENSAP	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	N/A								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Schema of data collected by the middleware (preferably in json format)								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	N/A								
Component/s	N/A								
Date (change history)	21.12.2018; 03.03.2020; 29.04.2020								

RQ ID	CO-T-05		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Specifications/definitions of machine cycles in each end user scenario.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The duration of production the completes a machine cycle, which is necessary when designing machine learning algorithms to predict the future states.								
Reporter	CORE				Assignee		HOLONIX, ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, SENSAP		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	N/A								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Start / stop records or key, value pair encoding								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	N/A								
Component/s	Inference Engine								
Date (change history)	21.12.2018; 03.03.2020; 29.04.2020								

RQ ID	CO-T-06		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Specifications and documentation of the historical data.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	To design proper machine learning algorithms with increased interpretability by the end users, expert knowledge of the data (what, why, how, etc.) needs to be provided by the end users in the form of documentation.								
Reporter	CORE				Assignee		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	N/A								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Enough data to train algorithms. Ideal number of samples > 500.								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	N/A								
Component/s	Inference Engine								
Date (change history)	21.12.2018; 03.03.2020; 29.04.2020								

TAU

Active and passive component bonding processes in micro-optics

RQ ID	TA-T-01		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases #		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, HiLase	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	No	<i>Rejected</i>	No		
Parent RQ	N/A									
Title (Summary)	Prototyping micro-optics assemblies									
Rationale (why, what, how)	A versatile and easily reconfigurable platform is needed to demonstrate many different types of zero-defect micro-optics assemblies for relatively small quantities (from several to some tens of assemblies). In order to define new assemblies fast, the platform should have advanced (semi) automatic calibration routines to define reference positions for the tooling and work benches. Moreover, the calibration routines could include visual or electronic inspection and recognition of tooling based for example on QR codes, visual inspection vs library or electronic IDs to verify correct tooling and quickly recalibrate their positions. The assembly system software should enable efficient teaching of motion trajectories using manual position guidance supported by cameras in a 3D environment.									
Reporter	TAU				Assignee			All manufactures		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No		
Pre-conditions	The opto-electro-thermo-mechanical design of a micro-optics assembly/use case and a modular process chain model.									
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	A relatively short set-up time of assembly station for different prototyped micro-optics assemblies compared to the process chain complexity, required tolerances, and assembly process.									
Exceptions	N/A									
Dependencies	The RQ has several dependencies such as KBS, DSS, visual inspection methodologies, smart tagging, process chain model, process control architecture, assembly station layout and use case.									
Component/s	The components of the micro-optics assembly, the assembly platform, process chain model, and a data base where the process parameters are stored.									
Date (change history)	19.12.2018; 17.02.2020; 14.04.2020									

RQ ID	TA-T-02		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases #		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, HiLase	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	No	<i>Rejected</i>	No		
Parent RQ	TA-T-01									
Title (Summary)	Metrology enhanced tooling for UV-bonding									
Rationale (why, what, how)	In order to mitigate the alignment issues caused by the shrinkage of UV-adhesives, the movement during the curing could be traced by measuring the relative position of the fastened optical component using optical interferometry. Recorded movement may indicate that the gluing process is defective and the output may not fulfill quality requirements. Furthermore, metrology enhanced tooling can adaptively compensate the movement during the UV-curing. Such functionality would allow faster set-up time and lower prototyping cost as one could simply measure glue shrinkage for each assembly component rather than to find out it through iterative process. Moreover, in production environment tooling could be used to monitor if glue shrinks in a constant way from day to day – this could be great help for zero defect manufacturing to find defective components. Practical realizations of this type of tooling include various different optical metrology instruments like e.g. different type of imaging or non-imaging interferometers.									
Reporter	TAU				Assignee			SENSAP, all other manufacturers		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	Yes		
Pre-conditions	The characterized surfaces of a micro-optic component must be flat. Moreover, the opto-mechanical design should enable an obstruction free optical path from the sensor to the characterized component surface.									
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	A measurement resolution that is reasonable compared to the movement of a micro-optic component during the UV-curing process. Moreover, the characterization time should not exceed the time required to assemble the component.									
Exceptions	Micro-optic components not satisfying the pre-conditions.									

D2.5 Strategy implementation report

Dependencies	Visual inspection methodologies, environmental sensor data, and inline metrology (i.e. SE-T-01)
Component/s	Process chain model, micro-optic assembly with components having high positioning tolerance requirements, and metrology sensors that can be used to carry out the measurements.
Date (change history)	19.12.2018; 17.02.2020; 15.04.2020

RQ ID	TA-T-03	RQ Type	Technical		Use Cases #	ALPES, BRIGTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	<x>	<i>Agreed</i>	<x>	<i>Baselined</i>	<x>	<i>Rejected</i>	<x>
Parent RQ	TA-T-01							
Title (Summary)	Die/submount bonding							
Rationale (why, what, how)	Die/submount bonding with thin, uniform, and flux-free solder is required to achieve high reliability and low thermal resistance between the die and the heat sink. Moreover, after the die/submount bonding process, the solder joint quality must be investigated in order to avoid solder joint failures. The possible reworking, if the soldering process turns out to be defective, damaged, or misplaced, should follow the inspection. Scenario where soldered submount is reworked is realistic.							
Reporter	TAU			Assignee		All manufacturers		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No
Pre-conditions	The opto-electro-thermo-mechanical design of a micro-optics assembly/use case, a modular process chain model, and an assembly platform.							
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The bonding process should fulfill the alignment tolerance requirements of each use case. Moreover, the bonds should have acceptable quality (i.e. less than 5% of voids, no cracks, no delamination, no incomplete fill or overfill, low stress, thin filler layer, good electrical and thermal conductivity) with high reproducibility and cost efficiency.							
Exceptions	N/A							
Dependencies	KBS, DSS, smart tagging, visual inspection methodologies and CPS.							
Component/s	The process chain model, assembly architecture, the micro-optics components, and the data base.							
Date (change history)	19.12.2018; 17.02.2020; 15.04.2020del							

RQ ID	TA-T-04	RQ Type	Technical		Use Cases #	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE, HiLase		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	No	<i>Rejected</i>	No
Parent RQ	AT-T-07							
Title (Summary)	Insitu testing of a chip, bar or submounted light source							
Rationale (why, what, how)	Insitu testing of components enables to identify a defective light source, to address the source causing the indicated defect, and to define the possible changes in the supply chain. The insitu testing is carried by beam diagnostic tool (BDT) that supports both testing and assembly.							
Reporter	TAU			Assignee		TAU, FIC, F-IOF, SENSAP		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	Yes	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No
Pre-conditions	The opto-electro-thermo-mechanical design of a micro-optics assembly/use case, a modular process chain model and an assembly platform.							
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The technical acceptance criteria depend on the applied use case. However, the RQ must be simple to use, flexible and versatile in the sense that it can be applied for different type of assemblies and applications. The BDT should include at least power measurement and beam profiling capabilities.							
Exceptions	N/A							
Dependencies	KBS, DSS, smart tagging, visual inspection methodologies and CPS.							
Component/s	Insitu beam diagnostic tool, measurable components and assemblies, process chain model and a data base to store and retrieve data.							
Date (change history)	19.12.2018; 17.02.2020; 15.04.2020							

POLIMI

Evaluation of functionalities and downstream strategies

RQ ID	PO-T-01	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Definition of technically feasible defect management strategies.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The identified defect management strategy that will be defined for each defect type, selecting among (i) defect repair by downstream compensation, (ii) disassembly for direct reuse of components, or (iii) disassembly for reuse through remanufacturing and regeneration, shall be technically feasible, meaning that the required skills, technologies, tools and methods shall be accepted by the end-users.								
Reporter	POLIMI			Assignee			ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Clear formalization of the currently known defect types and the related inspection and characterization procedures is available. The company already owns the competences for technically implementing the processes related to the developed defect management strategies.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The identified defect management strategies are validated by the company and can be replicated by the company at industry scale.								
Exceptions	Recycling competence may be not owned by the company but connection with other companies owning such competences can be created.								
Dependencies	-								
Component/s	-								
Date (change history)	20.01.2019.; 16.03.2020; 25.05.2020								

RQ ID	PO-T-02	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	PO-T-01								
Title (Summary)	Defect repair by downstream compensation								
Rationale (why, what, how)	A model-based approach for the determination of compensation variables and entities shall be applicable to the end-user case, and the nominal process settings shall be adjustable depending on the conditions of the defective part.								
Reporter	POLIMI			Assignee			ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	It is possible to adjust the nominal input variables or parameters of the correlated process.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	It is feasible to adjust the process settings within 5-10 seconds, without negatively affecting the cycle time.								
Exceptions	None.								
Dependencies	PO-T-01								
Component/s									
Date (change history)	20.01.2019.; 16.03.2020; 25.05.2020								

RQ ID	PO-T-03	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	PO-T-01								
Title (Summary)	Disassembly for direct reuse of components.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The functionality of the reusable component shall be preserved after the disassembly process, meaning that non-destructive disassembly shall be applied.								
Reporter	POLIMI			Assignee			ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Samples or nominal characteristics of the product to be disassembled are available. The disassembly competences are owned by the target company.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The cost of the disassembly process does not exceed the cost of recycling. The cost of the disassembly process does not exceed the cost of the equivalent production process for an equivalent new part. The disassembly time is compliant with the cycle time of the main process chain.								
Exceptions	None								
Dependencies	PO-T-01								
Component/s									
Date (change history)	20.01.2019.; 16.03.2020; 25.05.2020								

RQ ID	PO-T-04	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	PO-T-03								
Title (Summary)	Component design for non-destructive disassembly.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The component suitable for reuse should be designed with the purpose to be reversibly disassembled, meaning that irreversible joints, such as glue and welding, should be absent.								
Reporter	POLIMI			Assignee			ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	The product is designed by the company, hence the re-design process presents some degrees of freedom.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The time for disassembling the re-designed component is more than 10% lower than the time to disassemble the original component, while the cost is not significantly higher.								
Exceptions	Products that do not present re-design degrees of freedom.								
Dependencies	PO-T-03								
Component/s									
Date (change history)	20.01.2019.; 16.03.2020; 25.05.2020								

RQ ID	PO-T-05		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	PO-T-01										
Title (Summary)	Disassembly for reuse through remanufacturing and regeneration.										
Rationale (why, what, how)	Remanufacturing and regeneration should be technically feasible and should preserve the functionality of the component.										
Reporter	POLIMI				Assignee			ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	Remanufacturing and re-use are not negatively perceived by the target customers or the performance of the remanufactured product can be safely downgraded.										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The performance of the remanufactured product is the same or better than those of the original product, or in any case within the tolerance values, in case of product destination re-direction or downgrading.										
Exceptions	None										
Dependencies	PO-T-01										
Component/s											
Date (change history)	20.01.2019.; 16.03.2020; 25.05.2020										

RQ ID	PO-T-06		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	PO-T-05										
Title (Summary)	Remanufacturing of components for reuse.										
Rationale (why, what, how)	Remanufacturing should bring back the quality and the geometry of the component to the “as good as new” conditions.										
Reporter	POLIMI				Assignee			ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	Remanufacturing and re-use are not negatively perceived by the target customers.										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The performance of the remanufactured product is the same or better than those of the original product.										
Exceptions	None										
Dependencies	PO-T-05										
Component/s											
Date (change history)	20.01.2019.; 16.03.2020; 25.05.2020										

RQ ID	PO-T-07		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	PO-T-05								
Title (Summary)	Remanufacturing of components for reuse.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The remanufacturing process should be less energy intensive than the production of the new component, should be less expensive, and accepted by the customer.								
Reporter	POLIMI			Assignee			ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Remanufacturing of individual components is feasible and the disassembly process is such that that component is liberated.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The performance of the remanufactured component is the same or better than those of the original component.								
Exceptions	None								
Dependencies	PO-T-05								
Component/s									
Date (change history)	20.01.2019.; 16.03.2020; 25.05.2020								

CPS for product reuse and requalification

RQ ID	PO-T-08		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Cyber-physical system (CPS) architecture definition.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The architecture of the CPS should be properly integrated within the iQonic system architecture.								
Reporter	POLIMI			Assignee			FRAUNHOFER		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Input data required by the CPS are available, collected, correctly stored and reliable. The output of the CPS is processable by the operator without additional skills and efforts.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Increase of the output component yield by 20% at least, while not interfering considerably with the cycle time.								
Exceptions									
Dependencies	None								
Component/s	None								
Date (change history)	20.01.2019.; 16.03.2020; 25.05.2020								

RQ ID	PO-T-09	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	PO-T-08								
Title (Summary)	CPS data gathering module.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The data gathering module of the CPS shall be connected to the Knowledge Base System (KBS) to continuously receive in input updated information about the product at the previous production stages before requalification.								
Reporter	POLIMI			Assignee			HOLONIX		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Data feeding the CPS are available in the Knowledge Base								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Data are stored when needed in a format that is readable by the CPS.								
Exceptions	None								
Dependencies	PO-T-08								
Component/s									
Date (change history)	20.01.2019.; 16.03.2020; 25.05.2020								

RQ ID	PO-T-10	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	PO-T-08								
Title (Summary)	CPS intelligent data analysis module.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The intelligent module of the CPS, where the most proper solution for requalification is selected depending on the product conditions, should guarantee a computational time that is shorter than the lead time between the stage where data are gathered and the stage where the requalification takes place (requalification does not create blocking).								
Reporter	POLIMI			Assignee			HOLONIX		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	The physical dependencies among the component key quality features and the assembled module key quality features are known to the company.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The physics base modelling is accepted by the company.								
Exceptions	None								
Dependencies	PO-T-08								
Component/s									
Date (change history)	20.01.2019.; 16.03.2020; 25.05.2020								

RQ ID	PO-T-11	RQ Type			Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	PO-T-08								
Title (Summary)	CPS actuation module.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The CPS should influence the quality characteristics of the component by acting automatically or manually on the downstream process parameters.								
Reporter	POLIMI				Assignee			HOLONIX	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	The actuation capabilities are available in the current process settings or are potentially integrable in the production equipment.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	The adaptation of the process parameters, or part routing, or both takes place in reasonably short time and does not interfere with the current cycle time.								
Exceptions	None.								
Dependencies	PO-T-08								
Component/s									
Date (change history)	20.01.2019.; 16.03.2020; 25.05.2020								

RQ ID	PO-T-12	RQ Type			Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	PO-T-08								
Title (Summary)	CPS data exchange.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The data exchange protocol among the physical layer and the digital layer of the CPS should be based on machine-to-machine communication standards such as OPC-UA.								
Reporter	POLIMI				Assignee			HOLONIX	
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	The selected protocol, i.e. OPC-UA, is supported by the available equipment.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria									
Exceptions	None.								
Dependencies	PO-T-08								
Component/s									
Date (change history)	20.01.2019.; 16.03.2020; 25.05.2020								

RQ ID	PO-T-13	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	CPS Human-machine Interface (HMI).								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The HMI reporting to the operator the suggested requalification for re-use action shall make it possible to (i) report to the operator the defect cause and the suggested correction action, (ii) suggest to the operators specific procedures for requalification depending on the component defect entity, (iii) let the operator accept the suggested strategy or manually select a different strategy for requalification.								
Reporter	POLIMI			Assignee			ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	The company experience in using advanced HMIs has to be available.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	50% of the workers in the specific production area can interpret the output of the CPS visualized in the built HMI.								
Exceptions	Language issues.								
Dependencies									
Component/s									
Date (change history)	20.01.2019.; 16.03.2020; 25.05.2020								

FORTH

The adaptive in-process optics for real time and thin layer quality inspection

RQ ID	FO-T-01	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases		ALPES	
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	N/A								
Title (Summary)	Definition of defects in thin-layers, hard-mask adhesion.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	The definition identification and characterization of the defects that affect the quality of hard-mask adhesion in thin-film growth can apply to the optical correction strategy. This shall dictate the adjustment of the adaptive in-process optics imaging setup to meet the optical sensitivity needed to identify those defects. The definition of the defects that will be imaged, shall provide the base for the calculation and implementation of the optical parameters of the thin layer quality inspection, for various front-end processing stages.								
Reporter	FORTH			Assignee			ALPES		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Causes of defect types should be defined								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Characterization and categorization of defects in terms of type, size and impact, in hard-mask adhesion process in ALPES wafers.								
Exceptions	N/A								
Dependencies	FO-T-01								
Component/s	Definition of defects in thin-layers, hard-mask adhesion.								
Date (change history)	29.12.2018; .26.02.2020; 30.09.2020								

SHADOW

General

RQ ID	SRC-T-01		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases #		FILAR		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	N/A										
Title (Summary)	Feasibility study of automating the crystal rod grinding and polishing process										
Rationale (why, what, how)	Automatizing the crystal rod grinding process will enhance quality and improve production efficiency. This requirement will be broken down into five subtasks SRC-T-02 (Grasp control), SRC-T-03 (Grasp Quality), SRC-T-04 (Grasp stabilization), SRC-T-05 (impedance control) (optional) & SRC-T-06 (Learning by demonstration) (optional).										
Reporter	FILAR				Assignee			SHADOW			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	N/A										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	This task will tell us if the system allows us to perform the task within the required quality parameters and in case of failure it will inform us about the required improvements to make it possible.										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	SRC-T-02, SRC-T-03, SRC-T-04, SRC-T-05, SRC-T-06										
Component/s	Grasp control subsystem, Grasp quality metrics, Arm impedance control, Learning by demonstration										
Date (change history)	21.12.2018; 25.02.2020; 23.04.2020										

RQ ID	SRC-T-02		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases #		FILAR		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	SRC-T-01										
Title (Summary)	Improvement of Shadows hand grasp control										
Rationale (why, what, how)	Development should be made on Shadows hand to improve grasp control. Improving the hands ability to execute the actions involved in grasping (pre-grasp, grasp, placement, etc.)										
Reporter	SHADOW				Assignee			SHADOW			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	N/A										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Hand system grasping capability will be improved.										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	N/A										
Component/s	Grasp control subsystem										
Date (change history)	25.02.2020; 23.04.2020										

RQ ID	SRC-T-03		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases #		FILAR		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	SRC-T-01										
Title (Summary)	Improvement of Shadows hand grasp quality.										
Rationale (why, what, how)	Development should be made on Shadows hand to improve grasp quality. Development of grasp quality metrics to identify best grasp position and assess grasp quality.										
Reporter	SHADOW				Assignee			SHADOW			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	N/A										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Grasp quality metrics will be produced.										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	N/A										
Component/s	Grasp quality metrics										
Date (change history)	25.02.2020; 23.04.2020										

RQ ID	SRC-T-04		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases #		FILAR		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	SRC-T-01										
Title (Summary)	Improvement of Shadows hand grasp stabilization										
Rationale (why, what, how)	Development should be made on the Shadows hand to improve grasp stabilization. Should attempt to maintain a stable grasp of the object during operation.										
Reporter	SHADOW				Assignee			SHADOW			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No			
Pre-conditions	N/A										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Grasp controller will react to improved grasp stability.										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	SRC-T-03										
Component/s	Grasp control subsystem										
Date (change history)	25.02.2020; 23.04.2020										

RQ ID	SRC-T-05		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases #		FILAR		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	SRC-T-01										
Title (Summary)	Apply impedance control to the shadow hand and arm system										
Rationale (why, what, how)	Impedance control is needed to maintain contact with grinding surface and maintain a constant pressure.										
Reporter	FRAUNHOFER				Assignee			SHADOW			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	Yes			
Pre-conditions	N/A										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Impedance control for the arm will be deployed.										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	N/A										
Component/s	Arm impedance control										
Date (change history)	25.02.2020; 23.04.2020										

RQ ID	SRC-T-06		RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases #		FILAR		
Status	<i>New</i>	No	<i>Agreed-to</i>	No	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No			
Parent RQ	SRC-T-01										
Title (Summary)	Test learning by demonstration techniques										
Rationale (why, what, how)	Learning by demonstration will allow a user's demonstration to teach the system to perform the task. We want to explore the approach where an operator uses teleoperation to control the robot while executing the task. This will prove that the hardware is capable of performing the task. Then the system can use these demonstrations to learn how to execute the task autonomously. We will need to develop the system to the point where the operator can execute the task correctly through the robot. For this we plan to use compliant control to facilitate exerting the appropriate force against the grinding surface. Finally, we will attempt to use learning by demonstration to teach the system how to perform the task autonomously.										
Reporter	SHADOW				Assignee			SHADOW			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	Yes			
Pre-conditions	N/A										
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Possible learning by demonstration techniques will be explored in order to use teleoperation data to perform the task autonomously.										
Exceptions	N/A										
Dependencies	SRC-T-05										
Component/s	Learning by demonstration										
Date (change history)	25.02.2020; 23.04.2020										

HILASE (IP-ASCR)

High intensity diode pump solid state lasers (DPSSL)

RQ ID	IP-B-01	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases #		HiLASE	
Status	<i>New</i>	Yes	<i>Agreed</i>	Yes	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	FI-B-01, FI-B-02								
Title (Summary)	Selection of laser gain media and coatings								
Rationale (why, what, how)	In cooperation with FILAR select materials and coatings of main importance. Based on this selection, define KPF. According to existing knowledge propose most critical parameters in production chain and propose way of documenting them.								
Reporter	HiLase			Assignee			FILAR		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	A crystal from the FILAR production portfolio (alternatively an off-the-shelf crystal from other suppliers can be used) shall be analyzed and selected to be a laser gain media in thin-disk high-power laser applications. This depends on the crystal manufacturing, doping and coating capabilities at FILAR, based on the requirements made by HiLASE.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Accuracy and tolerance of crystal doping ratio, accuracy and tolerance of geometrical parameters of the thin-disk crystal (surface PV and roughness RMS, outer circumference cracks), coating quality (laser induced damage threshold LIDT).								
Exceptions	LIDT might be done externally.								
Dependencies	n.a.								
Component/s	Thin disk, Nd:Yag preferably, doped. Disk diameter ca. 10 mm, thickness ca. 0.1-0.2 mm, AR/HR coated								
Date (change history)	17.01.2019; 09.03.2020; 12.09.2020								

RQ ID	IP-B-02	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases #		HiLASE	
Status	<i>New</i>	Yes	<i>Agreed</i>	Yes	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	FI-B-01, FI-B-02								
Title (Summary)	Influence of mechanical processes to coatings quality on laser gain media								
Rationale (why, what, how)	Based on experience, HiLase team recognized that all mechanical processes (cutting, grinding, polishing, and cleaning) are strongly influencing final performance (LIDT as well as operation in the laser system) of laser gain media. In line with mentioned we propose to define KPFs, propose way of surface inspection after each mechanical process and document them.								
Reporter	HiLase			Assignee			FILAR		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Established process at FILAR to deliver coated, doped Nd:YAG disks.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	LIDT at successful parameters.								
Exceptions	Other commercially available thin-disk crystal might be used as reference.								
Dependencies	IP-B-01								
Component/s	Thin disk, Nd:Yag preferably, doped. Disk diameter ca. 10 mm, thickness ca. 0.1-0.2 mm, AR/HR coated								

D2.5 Strategy implementation report

Date (change history)	17.01.2019; 09.03.2020; 12.09.2020
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RQ ID	IP-B-03	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases #		HiLASE	
Status	<i>New</i>	Yes	<i>Agreed</i>	Yes	<i>Baselined</i>	Yes	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	FI-B-01 and-02, IP-B-01 and -02								
Title (Summary)	Testing of coated surfaces quality of laser gain media for laser applications.								
Rationale (why, what, how)	Prepared laser gain media (with well documented production parameters in each production step) will be tested at HiLase for LIDT (with HiLase laser systems) and their performance will be investigated in some real laser systems. Performance of laser gain media will be correlated with production parameters. In order to produce laser gain media with defined KPFs, it will be selected a way of improvements in each production step and will be designed monitoring and control systems.								
Reporter	HiLase			Assignee			iQonic Consortium		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No	
Pre-conditions	Established process at FILAR to deliver coated, doped Nd:YAG disks.								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	LIDT at successful parameters.								
Exceptions	Other commercially available thin-disk crystal might be used as reference.								
Dependencies	IP-B-02								
Component/s	Thin disk bonded on heat sink.								
Date (change history)	17.01.2019; 09.03.2020; 12.09.2020								

RQ ID	IP-B-04	RQ Type		Technical		Use Cases #		HiLASE	
Status	<i>New</i>	Yes	<i>Agreed</i>	Yes	<i>Baselined</i>	No	<i>Rejected</i>	No	
Parent RQ	iQonic system testing on production of thin-disk head								
Title (Summary)	Production of thin-disk head								
Rationale (why, what, how)	Production of thin-disk head is very complex with very low rate of success. Therefore, production of one head can take several months. This production can strongly benefit from usage of iQonic system while many similar problems (glue shrinking during bonding for example) will be addressed.								
Reporter	HiLase			Assignee			FRAUNHOFER		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	
Pre-conditions	Laser Crystal with specific dopant level and HR/AR coatings will have following dimensions: 10 mm - 0mm/+2 mm and thickness 110 or 220 μm with tolerance of +/- 10 μm . Surface roughness <math><\lambda/5</math> (200 nm) and flatness <math><\lambda/5</math> (200 nm) Heat sink (SiC) with surface flatness <math><\lambda/5</math> (200 nm)								
Acceptance/Fit Criteria	Crystal centring on the heat sink 0 mm +/- 100 μm , Adhesive gap 5 μm +/- 2 μm								
Exceptions	n.a								
Dependencies	Specially designed holder which will hold in place thin disk and heat sink and prevent bending (after bonding and during bonding) of thin disk								
Component/s	Laser material in the form of the thin disk, heat sink and adhesive material								

Date (change history)	17.01.2019; 09.03.2020; 04.05.2020
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